

D5.2 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (1st update)

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Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

biorural.eu

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BioRural Consortium

BioRural Consortium			
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2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALORIAL	VALORIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	IZES GGMBH	IZES	DE
6	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG-PIB	PL
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9	LATVIJAS LAUKSAIMNIECIBAS UNIVERSITATE	LLU	LV
10	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA	AVEBIOM	ES
11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA	CBE	PT
13	AIEL ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	FOODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION FOR ENTREPREUNERSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	FSH	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICO	EL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA ALGNE TEHNOLOGIJE, DOO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO
19	ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJ SKOPJE	GGP	MK

Executive Summary

BioRural seeks to establish a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. BioRural will contribute to bridge the gap between the novel high-end bio-based solutions currently available and the everyday rural life in Europe by:

- evaluating and assessing the current state of the European rural bioeconomy,
- identifying grassroots needs and ideas,
- fostering effective knowledge and information exchange,
- looking into potential opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

This way, BioRural will develop a transition framework towards a sustainable, regenerative, inclusive, and just circular Bioeconomy across all Europe at local and regional scale and support innovators to scale-up inclusive and small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas. To do so, the project will:

- (i) Assess and evaluate the **current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy** in the EU and identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (ii) Create four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that will form a **European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)**;
- (iii) Assess and promote **success stories** of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- (iv) Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool, named **BioRural Toolkit**;
- (v) Facilitate knowledge exchange and **capacity building** for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops in local, regional, and European level;
- (vi) Create **rural development blueprints** for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- (vii) Disseminate and communicate all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

The Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, provides the guidelines for effectively sharing information within the consortium and an extensive strategy for transferring project knowledge and results to the intended stakeholders.

This document is an update of the D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (DEC plan), providing information with regards to the progress and the monitoring of the plan's implementation by the project partners until M18.

The deliverable will be concluded with the documentation of the attained results of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (D5.3 Results of the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities with due date on M36).

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AKIS	Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems
DEC	Dissemination Exploitation and Communication
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and Sustainability
ERBN	European Rural Bioeconomy Network
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RBPs	Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SOSTAC	Situation, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Action, Control

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Summary

Challenge

The EU economy is heavily reliant on linear production systems and non-renewable resources and materials. Since the extraction of fossil fuels continues to release more carbon into the atmosphere, it exacerbates already major environmental and climatic issues and the well-known greenhouse effect. Further, climate change has an impact on the entire economy in addition to having an immediate consequence on the environment and humans.

The climate change impact over food security, human health, migratory flows, biodiversity loss and rising sea levels, will lead to a decline in productivity and wealth creation.

In this context, the bioeconomy has a key role to play.

Strengthening Europe’s bioeconomy can significantly accelerate progress towards achieving key EU policy objectives, such as transitioning to a circular economy, becoming climate neutral by 2050, and strengthening the EU industrial base.

BioRural aims to create a pan-European Rural Bioeconomy Network under which related stakeholders cooperate to promote the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas to increase the share of Bioeconomy, giving increased value in such remote areas. This framework will contribute to bridging the gap between the available novel high-end bio-based solutions and the everyday European rural life by assessing the existing situation of European rural Bioeconomy, capturing grassroots-level needs and ideas, promoting effective exchange of knowledge and information, and investigating the possible opportunities for regional development through the expansion of bio-based solutions integration in rural Europe.

BioRural is built on a three-pillar intervention scheme:

Table 1: BioRural three-pillar intervention scheme

Pillar 1 - Knowledge	Pillar 2 - Network	Pillar 3 – Business Models
<p>1 overview of the EU Bioeconomy current status</p> <p>440 interviews with end users/experts</p> <p>5 knowledge exchange workshops</p>	<p>1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)</p> <p>4 Regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms - RBPs</p> <p>8 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories</p> <p>42 capacity building workshops</p> <p>4 Regional workshops</p> <p>1 European Bioeconomy Challenge</p>	<p>5 Business model blueprints (for each of the main Bioeconomy themes)</p> <p>1 Post project sustainability plan</p>

BioRural's key activities

BioRural's workplan is comprised of the following key activities:

- Assessment and evaluation of the current performance of the European rural Bioeconomy in the EU and identification of the factors affecting innovation, adoption, and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Creation of four regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) that form a European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN);
- Assessment and promotion of success stories of bio-based solutions in rural areas;
- Development and continuous optimization of an online open stakeholders' tool, named BioRural Toolkit;
- Facilitation of knowledge exchange and capacity building for the European rural Bioeconomy through a series of workshops in local, regional, and European level;
- Creation of rural development blueprints for regional and business scale-up of resilient and circular bio-based solutions in rural areas and
- Dissemination and communication of all activities for maximum visibility and rural Bioeconomy expansion.

Figure 1: BioRural's conceptual approach

1.2 BioRural Consortium

BioRural practices a “Multi Actor Approach”, as it includes 19 partners from 14 European countries representing research entities, extension services, associations, SMEs, and innovation brokers. The consortium is very well framed by 8 Research entities on Bioeconomy, 4 of which are core partners of BIOEASTsUP project, 4 partners that are focused on innovation brokerage, social integration of novel solutions and business development, 2 SMEs representing Bio-based industry together with the 6 other success stories participating as subcontractors and 5 professional associations and extension touching end-users in the core.

Research: P1-CERTH (GR), BioRural coordinator, has broad expertise on bio-based solutions and has been involved in key H2020 projects in the field. P5-IZES (DE) is specialised in biogas systems and waste management to produce bio-fertiliser and compost. P6-AU (DK) has hoary experience on bio-based solutions, designing new technologies and preparing training material. P7-IUNG is a leading research entity in bioenergy, LCA and training and will lead WP4 based on its experience on developing ICT Platforms. P8-VDU (LT) is WP1 leader as it has extensive experience in empirical social research among various rural actors, being familiar with participatory approaches and interdisciplinary research. P9-LLU (LV) specialises on life sciences and Bioeconomy aspects and produces training material on these subjects. P11-UC (PT) works

heavily on forest biomass handling, logistics and use for multiple purposes, as well as specialises on LCA of Biosystems. P16-UL (SI) leads WP3 as a University specialised in Bioeconomy issues especially related to forest management and inland aquatic production systems.

Association/Extension: P2-DELPHY (NL), P10-AVE (ES), P12-CBE (PT), P13-AIEL (IT) and P19-GEA (RO) are significant regional professional associations and extension services specialised in all aspects of Bioeconomy and will support BioRural with their extensive network of end-users in organising successful workshops and disseminating the project. They will also feed the RBP workshops and the European Challenge event with “ambassador” actors. P10-AVE will act as the leader of WP2 to create the ERBN.

Industry: P4-NP (FR) is a bioplastics SME providing knowledge on biomaterials and biotechnological aspects. P17-ALGEN (SI) is an SME specialised in wastewater treatment and microalgae production used for multiple purposes. Both companies will act as success stories and also as mentors to ideas from the workshops’ activity. Innovation and Social Sciences: P3-VAL (FR) is an innovation scheme running the largest network devoted in agri-food innovation, but also has expanded in other Bioeconomy sectors. 14 FSH (GR) is an SME that works as innovation broker in Bioeconomy and has high expertise in dissemination/communication activities, but also in business models and open calls organisations in EU projects. P15-ICO (GR) works heavily on social innovation to assist on integrating environmentally friendly bio-based solutions in modern society. Finally, P18-GGP (NMK) is an active innovation broker with participation in EU projects and significant national activity.

A main advantage of the BioRural consortium is that the core team has previously or is collaborating in EU projects, being already familiar with project management, communication, and decision-making workflows to enable smooth and timely implementation of BioRural. The consortium has received 6 letters of acceptance to act as Advisors and 32 letters of support by Bioeconomy stakeholders that recognize the potential of BioRural.

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is an update on the D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, providing information with regards to the monitoring of the plan’s implementation by the project partners.

The document will be concluded with the documentation of the attained results of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (M36).

This document is comprised of the following chapters & Annexes:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project and the document’s scope, structure, and objectives.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project’s DEC methodology and approach, the identified target groups, and relevant key messages.

Chapter 3 delves into the specific dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels including the visual identity, communication material and the channel mix.

Chapter 4 specifies the reporting and monitoring procedures and tools, focusing on KPIs and the specific activities that are carried out.

Chapter 5 presents the identified Key Exploitable Results, the potential pathways to bring BioRural results to all targeted user communities as well as the identified IPRs and IPR strategy followed by the project partners.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

Annex A provides the project logo variations.

Annex B presents BioRural's covers that are used on social media.

Annex C provides images of the dissemination and communication material that has already been designed including the brochure, the banner, and the press release template.

Annex D provides the deliverable template.

Annex E provides the event planning template to be used for gathering information from partners regarding the events they are already planning on attending.

Annex F provides the synergy mapping template that partners complete with information on existing projects, networks, alliances etc., that they are currently part of and could be relevant to BioRural.

Annex G provides the publication planning template that partners complete with information on peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other planned publications.

Annex H provides the project's brand book.

Annex I provides the template for the Identification of new KERs & IPR process.

2 DEC methodology and approach

2.1 BioRural DEC Time plan [including after the end of the project]

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 2) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the achievement of the objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Vision, Phase 2: Raise cognition, Phase 3: Multiplier effect, Phase 4: Sustainability) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 2: BioRural's DEC phases

Important highlights until M18

During the time of submission of the deliverable, **phase 1** has been completed. More precisely, the design of the project's visual identity as well as the communication material including the brochure and banner have been developed along with their translation to all participating countries. Partners have made the initial mapping and outreach to the identified target groups and created liaisons with other EU funded projects working towards the common promotion of bioeconomy (D2.1 European Regional Bioeconomy Network creation and stakeholders mapping). BioRural partners have already progressed with the engagement of targeted stakeholders through their active participation in the project's activities and mainly the online workshops (T3.1. Online knowledge exchange on Bioeconomy) and multi-actor national workshops (T3.2 Generation of interactive and multi-actor innovation at national level). The aforementioned tasks are in progress. At the current point (**Phase 2**), BioRural has demonstrated eight (8), small-scale bio-based solutions, success stories coming from all European countries in which the BioRural consortium operates (T2.3: Innovation processes of selected success stories) and initiated the process for the identification of additional ones (T2.4: Identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform).

2.2 DEC methodology

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and provides a concrete roadmap for partners to boost the growth of the BioRural ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level. The BioRural DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC** model which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control.

Figure 3: BioRural DEC methodology

Situation analysis: A state-of-play analysis in which the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.

Objectives: The DEC plan elaborates upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication.

Tactics: Identification of the tactics that allow the BioRural consortium to implement its strategy.

Actions: The DEC plan builds upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the GA and includes the contribution expected from the partners over the project duration. A living list of planned events has been created. Open Science practices are being factored into all aspects of the DEC implementation.

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the GA, are used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting are also used and are presented in Chapter 4.

2.3 Multi-actor approach

BioRural uses a multi-actor approach, considering all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to achieve the project aims and ensure broad communication from the start. Figure 4 presents the six different stakeholders' groups that are involved in BioRural.

Figure 4: BioRural's stakeholder's groups

Interactive innovation process

The 'multi-actor' approach is key for interactive innovation. The way diverse actors work well together (the 'multi-actor approach') is crucial for interactive innovation to deliver unique project results and benefits.

Multi-actor innovation brings together a diverse range of public and private innovation actors as shown in figure 4, with complementary types and sources of knowledge to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs.

The multi-actor approach of BioRural requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach', facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. Taking a 'bottom-up' approach to development, allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation. Interactive innovation is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach. Multi actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and codesign practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems.

The process of interactive innovation followed by BioRural involves a series of specific scenarios and tools (based upon the LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook)¹, shown in Figure 5. These range from engaging and incentivising actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, to applying new knowledge on the ground.

¹ <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 5: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

For each of the above mentioned 6 key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have already been tested during the proposal stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritisation of the identified stakeholders’ groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritisation has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that BioRural aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders’ groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritisation process is presented in Figure 6.

Prioritisation of Stakeholders

Figure 6: Prioritisation of Stakeholders

Other tools that will be used for engaging stakeholders throughout the project implementation refer to understanding stakeholders and registering their needs with service design methods such as Personas².

Scenario 2:

² <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/personas>

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used for understanding the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences. The Journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATING

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised. The tool has been used during the project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation. TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

The tool has been used during the project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans. The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

Multi-actor approach & DEC actions

The project's multi-actor approach is extended to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partner's languages;
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end user;

- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society, and government;
- Capitalising on partners existing connections, networks, and events program;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs.

Material including the project brochure and banner has been translated into the languages of the partner countries and the responsibility has been assigned to specific partners (See Table 2).

Table 2: Translation task among partners

Partner		Language	
	NL		
	FR		
	DE		
	DK		
	PL		
	LT		
	LV		
	ES		
	PT		
	IT		
	GR		
	SI		
	RO		
	MK		

2.4 Target groups

Defining the project’s target audience is a critical step for focusing objectives and pursuing meaningful impact. A clear understanding of the target audiences (e.g., who they are, where they are, what are their needs and their typical characteristics) is an essential part of an effective DEC plan. This is needed to ensure that communication and dissemination channels, as well as the planned and undertaken activities are maximising and extending the reach of the project results. This chapter presents the seven target groups that have been identified explaining the benefits they gain through their engagement to the project (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Target groups and respective benefits

2.3. DEC Objectives & KPIs

The DEC plan objectives are S.M.A.R.T (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time bound) and provide a verifiable trajectory towards clear milestones and an estimated timeline to attain the goals and ensure impact maximisation.

Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities are expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact. More specifically the dissemination activities will be carefully planned to ensure that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders are engaged early and actively participate during each of the project's phases. BioRural applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all the relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the below dissemination objectives:

- Bring together a critical mass of stakeholders and maximise outreach opportunities for BioRural with targeted messaging and customised content;
- Diffuse scientific and technological knowledge generated in the project and put it to productive use via capacity building under BioRural activities;
- Nurture collaborative relationships with projects, initiatives, pan-European networks of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and AKIS actors to avoid duplication of efforts, and capitalise on the results;
- Receive and utilise feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to make sure project developments are going in the right direction;
- Align and integrate dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of our reusable assets;
- Encourage new initiatives and support those already being carried out.

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, BioRural's exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring BioRural results to all targeted stakeholders (including bio-based raw material producers, bio-based industries, rural and urban

citizens, local and regional government, local rural schools and universities, NGOs, environmental and citizens’ groups and unions). A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project’s lifetime. The objectives of the project’s exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results.
- Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project’s results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

BioRural aims to capture the added value of project results, which will be valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project’s results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialization when possible

Communication Objectives

All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project’s results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered as communication activities. In essence, communication activities are focused on maximising the visibility of the project, through widely attracting a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project’s results and benefit from the project’s advancements. To achieve this, attention will be paid to adapt the communication means, the measures, and the content both to the need and knowledge levels of the target groups as well as to the status, progress and needs of the BioRural project. To ensure that the communication measures will effectively address the project’s expectations, communication objectives have been set:

- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability- oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage positive reception and acceptance by farmers, their advisors, policy makers;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels.

2.5 Key messages

Key messages will be used to articulate in a simple straightforward manner the unique benefit of engaging with BioRural. Specific key messages have been identified depending on the communication channel and tool selected.

Arising from the concepts previously mentioned, a set of “backbone” messages per target group have been defined, as the basis for a deeper approach, while aiming to highlight the advantages provided by BioRural. The following table presents the key messages per target group.

Table 3: Target audience, objectives & key messages

Target audience (WHO)	Communication objectives (WHY)	Communication Key messages (WHAT)
Bio-based raw material producers & industries	Long term competitiveness, linkages with bio-based industries, support for scaling. Improved access to renewable raw materials, direct support for scaling, rural job security and satisfaction.	“BioRural can add value to your business by connecting you with bioeconomy innovators and stakeholders. Discover trends and needs of the industry, enter new markets and expand network with end users, researchers and policy makers.”

Rural /urban citizens	Local ownership and economic opportunities, local redevelopment, increased environmental awareness, better quality of life, access to sustainable products	“Find out how bioeconomy and biobased practices and innovations can benefit your daily personal and professional life by getting to know BioRural project.”
Government, policy makers etc.	Knowledge on Bioeconomy and, realisation of its multiple benefits, receive policy recommendations, support local redevelopment and resilience	“Align with BioRural and get support in the design of policies towards innovation adoption and the diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural area in order to strengthen them, and to receive benefit nation-wide.”
Local rural schools, universities etc.	Growing environmental awareness, focus on inter- and transdisciplinary research, hands-on knowledge on Bioeconomy applications	“Contribute to the identification of latest technologies in bio-based solutions and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations with other academia stakeholders across Europe.”
NGOs, environmental groups, citizen groups, think tanks	Platform for sharing ideas, knowledge and capacity, access to practical and scientific Bioeconomy knowledge	“Join BioRural networks and gain knowledge and tools for the adoption of circular bio-based proven solutions supporting the development of the wider circular bioeconomy.”
Private sector, Bioeconomy unions/projects	Sustainable business activities, access to sustainable raw materials, multi-actor partnerships, and improved impacts	“Be at the forefront of Bioeconomy developments and take advantage of opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.”

Specific communication tools and channels have been scheduled to reach the identified target groups:

Table 4: Communication tools and channels for target audience Channels, tools, and activities

Communication tools and channels	Bio-based raw material producers	Bio-based industries	Rural /urban citizens	Government, policy makers etc.	Local rural schools, universities etc.	NGOs, group, citizen groups, think tanks	Private sector, Bioeco-nomy unions/projects
Website & social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E-newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press outreach	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Interviews and outreach videos	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Networking, synergies & liaison activities				✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific, industry and policy publications	✓	✓		✓	✓		

3 Channels, tools and activities

This chapter outlines the communication tools and channels that will be used to connect with the BioRural target groups.

3.1 Visual identity

To target the broadest possible audience, BioRural has created a strong, memorable brand that visually reflects the unique identity and objectives of the project. BioRural will exploit multiple digital platforms to share updates and results and to facilitate ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. Posts, and other inputs will be curated to the target audiences at a frequency that demonstrates consistency and accessibility.

3.1.1 Visual identity and moto

The visual identity is the visible representation of the project. A strong visual identity combines images, colours, and shapes to create a powerful, memorable message to the viewer. BioRural 's visual identity was created considering the following:

- ✓ **Simplicity:** The selected visual identity must be able to tell the story in a simple manner.
- ✓ **Relevance:** An appropriate aesthetic that can be easily correlated with the project objectives.
- ✓ **Uniqueness:** The elements selected must lead to the design of a recognisable and unique visual identity.
- ✓ **Versatility:** A logo that can be easily used in different communication channels (digital and printed).

The logo will be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, brochures, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. Eight logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex A). The most frequently used logo for the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below:

Figure 8: BioRural logo

3.1.2 The use of the EU emblem

BioRural's deliverables are following the requirements set out by the European Commission and will include the EU flag and the source of funding as follows.

Funded by the European Union

Figure 9: EU Emblem

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages.³³

3.1.3 Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”⁴⁴

3.1.4 Colour palette

The colour palette was selected to represent the project’s values. The colours are optimised for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is high enough for black and white printing. The project's brand book is provided in Annex H.

Figure 10: BioRural colour palette

3.1.5 Templates

BioRural will be presented in numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results.

A **presentation template (ppt)** has been designed in line with the BioRural’s graphic identity to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/

⁴ Based on the Annotated Model Grant Agreement: [V0.2 DRAFT– 30.11.2021](#). For any changes, the DEC plan will be updated accordingly.

Figure 11: BioRural presentation template

The BioRural **deliverable template (doc)** is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number, and title) as well as the author's details.

Figure 12: BioRural deliverable template

3.2 BioRural channel mix

3.2.1 Website

The project’s website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BioRural’s stakeholders’ access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added- value and the impact of bio-based solutions in rural areas. The site will be regularly updated with contributions from all partners. It will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. Finally, the website is mobile friendly, increasing accessibility and maximising the impact of the project.

BioRural’s website has a twofold role as it serves as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project’s aims, providing new updates, documents for download and enabling access to the project’s social media accounts, and it also acts as a resource centre for research on topics related to biobased solutions and innovations mainly for rural areas, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3, the BioRural website is hosted at www.biorural.eu and contains the following sections and features.

Home/Landing page

The section includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube), a button for sign-up in the BioRural’s newsletter and navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project. It also includes a button leading to the BioRural Toolkit and Network.

Figure 13: BioRural website home page

The Project

The section includes the following elements:

- **About BioRural:** Presenting information about the project aim and specific objectives.
- **Bioeconomy State-of-play:** Presenting some key information about Bioeconomy in the EU and the contribution of the project to address the challenges faced.
- **BioRural Toolkit & Network:** Presenting the BioRural toolkit which is an online repository of bio-based solutions that enables the interaction between rural actors and provides the ground for wider application of bio-based solutions. Presentation of the Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) and the 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms (RBPs) is also included. The section provides direct access to users in order to access the Toolkit and register to the Network.

- **Partners:** Presenting the project consortium and providing active links to their respective websites.
- **Deliverables:** Providing links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo.
- **Rural Bioeconomy Alliance:** Presenting a cluster of EU-funded projects aimed at accelerating and supporting the development of circular rural Bioeconomy. BioRural has established this network along with other 10 projects.

Figure 14: BioRural website - "The Project" tab

Success stories

The section includes a presentation of the success stories gathered throughout the project duration. Currently, the section includes the 8 success stories that have been identified and mentioned in the GA and progressively will be enriched with the additional ones that will be identified under WP2 European Rural Bioeconomy Network and Success Stories.

Figure 15: BioRural website "Success stories" tab

Newsroom

The section contains the project Press releases as well as the events and project's news informing target stakeholders about the project's current and upcoming activities. The media kit also available in this section, provides access to all the project communication material (e.g., logo, brochure, banner).

Latest News

Figure 16: BioRural website "Newsroom" tab

Contact us

All the contact information of the BioRural project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with the project's stakeholders.

Figure 17: BioRural website "Get in touch" tab

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the BioRural website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

Privacy Policy

This privacy policy governs the use of your personal data by BioRural project – this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101060766 –; communicate with us via email, telephone, the contact form available on the website and our social media channels; e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube (hereafter referred to as "Social Media Channels"); or interact with us at fairs and events.

NOTE: If you want information on how we process personal data via cookies on our Website, you are kindly referred to our Cookie Policy.

1. Who is responsible for the processing of your personal data?

1.1 Your personal data are processed by Foodscale Hub, dissemination and communication partner of BioRural project – this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101060766. You can contact us via email at info@biorural.eu.

1.2 Foodscale Hub reserves the right to modify, change or amend this Privacy Policy at its own discretion and from time to time. Such modifications, changes or amendments shall be communicated via the Website. In case of questions or comments with regard to the modifications, changes or amendments, you can inform us by sending an e-mail to info@biorural.eu.

2. What categories of personal data do we process?

Figure 18: BioRural website "Privacy Policy" tab

Cookies Policy

1. What are Cookies?

"Cookies" are small text files that are stored on your computer through the Internet browser, only retaining information related to your preferences and therefore not including your personal data.

2. What are Cookies for?

Cookies help determine the usefulness, interest and number of uses of your websites, allowing for faster and more efficient browsing, eliminating the need to repeatedly enter the same information.

3. What type of Cookies do we use?

There are two groups of cookies that can be used:

Permanent Cookies: These are cookies that are stored in the browser in your access equipment (PC, mobile and tablet) and are used whenever you visit our website more than once. They are generally used to direct the browsing to the user's interests, allowing us to provide a more personalized service.

Figure 19: BioRural website "Cookies Policy" tab

FSH provided a template enabling partners to contribute to the site's content and describe their specific role and activities in the project:

Partner description for the website	
Full name of the partner	
Short name of the partner	
Country	
Website	
Short description of the partner	
Short description of the partner's role in the project	

Figure 20: Template for Partners description

Important highlights until M18

During the time of submission of the deliverable, the BioRural project's website demonstrated remarkable performance and engagement. The captivating and insightful content drew substantial interest, as evidenced by the significant number of clicks and visits. Visitors displayed genuine curiosity in exploring the project's achievements, underscoring the effectiveness of the presented information. Based on the analytics below, **2.8K unique users** visited our website and explored its content for almost a minute.

Figure 21: BioRural website analytics [01 September 2022 - 17 January 2024]

3.2.2 Digital and printed outreach

3.2.2.1 Social media

The project aims to have a strong social media presence and establish two-way communication channels, to better reach and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, five (5) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

- The most **cost-effective** set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups;
- The most **adequate, valid, and powerful** media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders and
- The most **popular** social media platforms to communicate and interact with various stakeholders.

BioRural is registered and active in LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare and YouTube since M3 and has established metrics for each channel to monitor its effectiveness and implement mitigation measures when necessary.

Figure 22: BioRural's social media channels

The social media described above have been selected to further enhance the multi-actor approach of the project. Different kinds of stakeholders require different means of approach. In that sense, the following characteristics have been taken into account:

- **Facebook:** This channel is used mainly for building relationships and keeping contact with peers and contacts. It is a good platform for building loyalty of the existing network base. Because of the plain language and messages, the content can reach out to several target groups regardless of social and business backgrounds. BioRural will use this channel to reach biobased professionals, rural /urban citizens, training institutions, NGOs, citizen groups, think tanks by sharing any project and partner news and updates.
- **Twitter:** This channel is used mainly for building awareness and enhancing public relations. Twitter is also often used to provide real time updates. BioRural will use this channel to reach regional or national governmental bodies, policy makers, research institutions, NGOs and media actors by focusing on workshops and events that will be happening throughout its course.
- **LinkedIn:** This channel is used mainly for creating awareness and generating networking and collaboration opportunities due to its professional character and style of communication. BioRural will use this channel to reach Bio-based innovators and professionals, Bioeconomy experts, think-tanks and other relevant stakeholders by promoting the creation of the ERBN and sharing updates about project key activities.
- **YouTube:** This channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes due to its character and features. BioRural will use this channel to reach any stakeholder interested in Bioeconomy by promoting the testimonial videos on the identified success cases, interviews, and outreach videos.
- **SlideShare:** This channel is mainly used for communication and education purposes. Project presentations will be uploaded for easy access to anyone interested.

To maximise visibility and impact of the project's events and outcomes, BioRural will exploit the consortium's already developed social media networks. This means that partners are expected to share, publish, and retweet content from BioRural's social media accounts and website, which will increase traction for project- related work and increase traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels.

After selecting the most appropriate channels there are several parameters to consider when the consortium will create social media content:

- ✓ **Interactivity** is the main pillar of the generated content and is the best way to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by non-specialists to facilitate interaction.
- ✓ **Eye-catching** posts will lead to higher conversions with prioritisation into visuals and graphics will make the piece unique.

- ✓ **Adaptability** of the social media assets to the format and functionality of the several devices. The asset will be used in such a frame to maximise their placement, especially taking into consideration the placement on mobile devices.

3.2.2.2 Social Media DOs & DON'Ts

BioRural has established a set of recommended actions on how partners should make social media posts in order to be efficient and effective.

DOs	DON'Ts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Follow BioRural on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube ✓ Use official institutional accounts to create social media posts ✓ Tag and repost content from the official BioRural channels to institutional & personal accounts ✓ Invite network contacts that may be interested in the BioRural updates ✓ Use the project logo and the EU emblem with the "Funded by the European Union" statement ✓ Use the BioRural hashtags 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Avoid using only your personal social media accounts to post, as posts created by personal accounts cannot count as KPIs ✗ Avoid creating social media accounts that mimic the BioRural project, as it might cause confusion and misunderstandings and have a negative impact on the project's accountability in social media platforms <div style="text-align: right; margin-top: 20px;"> </div>

Figure 23: BioRural's social media recommended actions

Social Media Strategy and Key Points

Social media posts are published on project's social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter with a standard frequency of at least one post per week and adjusted according to the project's needs. This social media strategy aims to maintain the audience's engagement and inform about various topics related to the project, which are presented below:

- Updates regarding partners event participation and project activities including webinars and workshops
- BioRural success stories
- BioRural toolkit
- Interesting reads, articles or news related to the project's main concepts
- BioRural featured in media outlets
- Newsletter & blog posts updates
- Relevant International Days

Followers/ subscribers of the BioRural social media channels are given the opportunity to react in posts, comment and spark conversations or repost the project's content, depending on the respective social media platform.

3.2.2.3 Hashtags

Creating hashtags that are relevant to the project and its outcomes will help reach target audiences and make it easy to find BioRural generated knowledge. Hashtags divide the project’s main topics into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and will help increase visibility in the social media environment, while they will make our messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Further tracking of the hashtags is going to help the consortium to analyse quantitative and qualitative data.

The project has set official distinctive hashtags such a **#BioRural**, **#Bioeconomy**, **#Rural**, **#circular**, **#biobasedinnovations** which are used to monitor the posts related to the project.

In addition, the hashtags **#HorizonEurope**, **#ResearchImpactEU**, suggested by the European Commission, accompany each post to emphasise the EU direction of the project.

LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn profile](#) was created to network with the BioRural target audiences and promote the project’s activities. As such, all the project’s news are published on its LinkedIn profile and partners have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes to attract a wider audience. Figure 24 provides an overview of BioRural’s LinkedIn profile.

Figure 24: BioRural LinkedIn profile

- **Current Status**

Figure 25 illustrates the project’s LinkedIn account’s visitor highlights over the course of the last one year [17 January 2023 – 17 January 2024]. **The page views reached 2,900, with 1,152 unique visitors and 32 custom button clicks.** Additionally, the graph shows that most visitors chose to navigate the project’s LinkedIn page from their desktop, with the mobile navigation also being of high preference.

Figure 25: BioRural LinkedIn account - Visitor highlights [17 January 2023 - 16 January 2024]

Regarding the LinkedIn page’s content, figure 26 presents the total impressions, reactions, comments and reposts that the page’s content sparked over the last year [17 January 2023 – 16 January 2024]. The content of the project’s LinkedIn page reached **45,574 impressions** in the last year, marking an important reach for the project’s communication. Respectively, the total reactions accounted for 2,662, with the comments accounting for 9 and the reposts for 113.

Figure 26: BioRural LinkedIn account - Visitor highlights [17 January 2023 - 16 January 2024]

Facebook

BioRural’s [Facebook page](#) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level. Figure 27 provides an overview of BioRural’s Facebook profile.

Figure 27: BioRural Facebook profile

● **Current Status**

Figure 28 presents the project’s Facebook page’s reach, regarding the period from 01 September 2022 to 17 January 2024. The total accounts reached throughout this period account for 9.1K, revealing an important potential audience for the project. The content interactions reached 2.2K, while the total followers are 279 and the link clicks 86.

Figure 28: BioRural Facebook Analytics [Performance 01 September 2022 - 17 January 2024]

Another important Facebook metric can be found in figure 29, where the page’s followers’ number, as well as their age and gender are presented. BioRural Facebook followers are divided almost evenly between men and women, while women in the age range of 35-44 are highlighted as the top audience amongst the Data4Food2030 Facebook followers.

Facebook followers ⓘ

279

Age & gender ⓘ

Figure 29: Followers' Age & Gender Division [01 September 2022 - 17 January 2024]

Twitter

A **Twitter account** was created to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policy makers and advisors. BioRural will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them, and post news, events, and updates on the project's status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter is also used to connect to "high influencers" in the research and business topics of the BioRural project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 30: BioRural Twitter profile

- **Current Status**

Figure 31 provides the BioRural Twitter analytics, focusing on the impressions of the account in January 2024. During this 29- days period, the BioRural Twitter account gained 1,000 impressions, gathering 8,3% engagement rate, 11 link clicks and 8 retweets.

Figure 31: BioRural Twitter analytics [January 2024]

SlideShare

A **SlideShare account** has been created to present project material in an engaging visual format that appeals to BioRural’s audience. Project presentations will be available for any interested stakeholder providing key information on the project implementation and activities.

BioRural

- 1 SlideShare
- 3 Followers
- 2 Followings

Edit

Personal Information

Occupation
BioRural

Presentations (1)

BioRural - General Presentatio...

1 year ago • 5 Views

Figure 32: BioRural SlideShare page

- **Current Status**

So far, 1 SlideShare with the BioRural general presented has been posted, gathering 5 views, while more presentations and other materials have been included in the plan for the upcoming months.

Presentations (1)

Figure 33: BioRural SlideShare analytics

YouTube

BioRural [YouTube Channel](#) is used to host and promote the project’s videos, including the 8 success stories, recordings of the online knowledge exchange workshops’ presentations, and, in general, the video content generated throughout the duration of the project.

Figure 34: BioRural YouTube page

● **Current Status**

The audiovisual material uploaded so far in the BioRural YouTube Channel is rich and diverse, including the BioRural success stories in a captivating format, as well as recordings from the 2 Knowledge - Exchange workshops, hosted by BioRural partners online. A total of 41 videos are divided into 3 playlists, depending on the topic, enabling easier access for the audience. Namely, so far, visitors can access the [BioRural Success Stories](#) playlist, the [Biochemicals & Biomaterials Knowledge Exchange Workshop](#) playlist, held on 25-27 October 2023 and the [Aquatic Systems Knowledge Exchange Workshop](#) playlist, held on 28-30 November 2023 (Figure 35).

Figure 35: BioRural YouTube Playlists Overview

Figure 36 presents an overview of the YouTube analytics, highlighting that BioRural achieved **1,406 views** so far, with 61,1 watch hours and 42 subscribers in total.

Figure 36: BioRural YouTube analytics [01 September 2022 - 17 January 2024]

3.2.2.4 Brochure

Brochures will be distributed at the project’s events (regional and National workshops, European Contest) as well as relevant events where the project can be promoted, to provide concise project information relevant to the target groups. A 3-fold brochure has been designed for this purpose and is presented below (Figure 37) as well as in Annex C along with its translated versions to all partners’ languages.

Figure 37: BioRural Brochure sides A&B

3.2.2.5 Banner

Banners will be used at physical events for eye-catching identification of the BioRural booth. Two versions of the banner have been created, with the latest to include the project’s social media as well as a QR code leading to the project website providing direct access to the project’s scope and activities. The BioRural banner is presented in Figure 38 and Annex C along with its translated versions to all partners’ languages.

Figure 38: BioRural Banner

3.2.3 Multiplier campaigns

3.2.3.1 Newsletter

An electronic newsletter is published on a six-month basis to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. It includes the latest developments, promotional material, as well as activities, upcoming events, and workshops.

Important highlights until M18

In total, **3 issues** of the BioRural newsletter have been published so far, gathering **197 newsletters subscriptions**. The issues have been promoted via BioRural's social media and website.

Biorural Newsletter [1st Issue](#)

Issue 1 of the newsletter was released on March 22nd, 2023, and was focused on introducing the project

and presenting the main actions taken by the project partners in the first 6 months since its kick off meeting.

Figure 39: Newsletter #1 overview

The 1st BioRural Newsletter included:

- An introduction to the project
- Kick-off meeting in Athens
- Meet the consortium
- Our Success Stories
- BioRural at a glance
- Recent BioRural activities
- Other Bioeconomy news

1st Newsletter Analytics

Figure 40 provides an overview of the 1st newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

1st Issue Newsletter Analytics

Top locations by opens

USA	70	39.3%
France	28	15.7%
Portugal	16	9.0%
Slovenia	12	6.7%
Romania	10	5.6%

Geographical distribution

Figure 40: Newsletter #1 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter [2nd Issue](#)

Issue 2 of the newsletter was released on 21/07/2023 and was focused on bringing the latest project updates to the audience, as well as announcing upcoming activities.

The 2nd BioRural Newsletter included:

- Announcement of the BioRural Toolkit upcoming release in September 2023
- Call interested stakeholders to join the European Rural Bioeconomy Network
- Our consortium travels around Europe: BioRural partners' activities
- BioRural joined the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance
- Latest BioRural synergies

Figure 41: Newsletter #2 overview

2nd Newsletter Analytics

Figure 42 provides an overview of the 2nd newsletter's analytics, regarding the audience's location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

Figure 42: Newsletter #2 Analytics

BioRural Newsletter 3rd Issue

Issue 3 of the newsletter was released on 22/12/2023 and was focused on bringing the latest project updates to the audience, as well as announcing upcoming activities.

Figure 43: Newsletter #3 overview

The 3rd BioRural Newsletter included:

- The launch of the BioRural Toolkit
- The promotion of our Knowledge - Exchange workshops on the BioRural YouTube channel
- The announcement of the upcoming Knowledge - Exchange workshops
- The BioRural national workshops in rural areas
- An overview of the BioRural national workshops in Spain, Lithuania and Greece
- The promotion of the BioRural Success stories videos on the BioRural YouTube channel
- The annual project meeting
- Wishes for the holiday season

3rd Newsletter Analytics

Figure 44 provides an overview of the 3rd newsletter’s analytics, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens and total clicks:

Figure 44: Newsletter #3 Analytics

Subscription to the newsletter is made through the project’s website. For the development of the newsletters a Mailchimp account has been created by FSH.

Figure 45: BioRural Newsletter subscription form

To achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, the BioRural partners are encouraged to promote the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Data security

BioRural pays special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the users’ personal data and newsletter recipients are asked to provide their consent prior to receiving any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data are fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BioRural Newsletter and all the collected data is stored and saved in the responsible partner’s servers. Data security is presented in the dedicated deliverable D6.3 Data Management Plan (M4), and particular attention has been given to safeguard the protection of personal data. A second iteration refers to Data security will be delivered (D6.4 Data Management Plan 1st update) in M36. Data security is paramount for BioRural, the protection of personal data will be ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies, like the use of HTTPS protocol for the encryption of all internet transactions and appropriate European and Internet security standards from ISO, ITU, W3C, IETF and ETSI. During the lifetime of the project IUNG-PIB will be responsible for the security of the BioRural’s Toolkit and FSH will be responsible for the security of the BioRural website, keeping regular backups and solving all the technical issues that will be raised in terms of the storage and representation of the data.

3.2.3.2 Press releases

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities, and developments to a broader audience as well as address specific stakeholders. The press releases are available on the BioRural s website under the tab “Newsroom”, and all related publications are shared on social media channels to disseminate the information.

The table below presents the indicative planning of the press releases based on the achieved milestones and tasks throughout the course of the project. A slight change has been made compared to the initial planning presented in D5.1 due to the progress of the project implementation.

Table 5: Press releases planning and status

Month	Press release content	Status
M2	linked to the project kick off (Milestone 1)	✓

M17	linked to the launch of the toolkit (Milestone 7) and the progress of the online and national workshops (T3.1 and T3.2)	✓
M19	linked to the national workshops and online workshops – progress update (T3.1 and T3.2)	(under preparation)
M21	linked to the announcement of the online call (T3.3.)	
M27	linked to the completion of RBP workshops (Milestone 5)	
M32	linked to the European bioeconomy challenge (Milestone 6)	
M34	linked to the identification of success stories in each Rural Bioeconomy Platform (Task 2.4)	
M35	linked to the completion of the business model blueprints	
M36	linked to the Policy guidelines for rural Bioeconomy development (T 3.4)	

To maximise influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is asked to translate all press releases into all consortium partners’ languages (14 in total). A press release template has been developed (Annex C) and shared with partners.

- The **first press release** has been created and distributed to the partners for translation and circulation to local/regional media. Relevant screenshots of the press release published in several local media outlets are presented below:

Figure 46: BioRural Press Release 1 in Greek and NMK media

- The **second press release**, informing the audience about the launch of the BioRural Toolkit, as well as mentioning the knowledge exchange and national workshops of the project, has already been created and distributed to the project partners for translation in order to circulate it to the local media outlets. Up to this point, the 2nd press release has been published on the BioRural website. Project partner GGP has circulated the press release in the magazine Moja Farma and is available [here](#).
- The **third press release** is under preparation. The content will relate to the progress of the online workshops under T3.1: Forestry and Habitats Workshop to take place on March 11-15, 2024, and

Bioenergy Workshop to take place on April 15-19, 2024. The press release will also include information about the progress of the national workshops under T3.2.

3.2.3.3 Interviews

Interviews in radio and TV will maximise the visibility of the project activities and reach a target audience that is not familiar with other digital channels such as the website and social media. The interviews will be focused on the promotion of key activities of the project (e.g. success stories, creation of the ERBN) and will be mainly targeted to the general public as well as bioeconomy actors (farmers, fishermen/women, foresters etc.).

3.2.3.4 Promotional videos

The BioRural consortium has developed marketing-style videos promoting the project’s success stories ([Success stories playlist](#)) as well as the innovators behind them. The videos are available on the project’s [YouTube channel](#). The first eight success stories are presented in the table below.

Table 6: Success stories to be promoted

Partner	Success story
	“Bio-based Garden” success story
	“Bioplastics” success story
Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation State Research Institute	“Pustelnia” success story
	“Latvia’s State Forests” success story
Search Biom Association	“Gasification and Biochar from olive waste” success story
	“SCIVEN” success story
	“Staramaki” success story
	“Algae production” success story

The list will be further enriched with the course of the project and the identification of additional success stories by the partners (M10-M36). In total **20 promotional videos** will be produced.

3.2.3.5 Podcast series

Podcasts are digital audio files presented in a series, typically with new instalments received automatically by subscribers. This on-demand technology is growing in popularity with listener penetration expected to reach or exceed 30% across Europe by 2030 according to recent data.

BioRural will create 2 podcast series of ten episodes in total, to enrich and diversify the website and address auditory learning styles. Content created by partners will follow an overarching theme that will

make for cohesive, entertaining series. The length of each episode will be around 15-20 minutes. The series will be available for free on Google Podcasts.

The two podcast categories will focus on the following categories:

- Commercial bio-based solutions & financing tools
- Capacity building on Bioeconomy including participating ideas of the European Bioeconomy Challenge

The podcast series will be developed during months 24-36.

BioRural foresees the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts to influence a wide range of targeted stakeholders and to promote the project and its findings. All publications will implement Open Access and open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

- far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- high likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

Scientific publications

For the scientific publications, the consortium will apply the Open Access Policy as described in OpenAIRE (<http://www.openaire.eu/>). More specifically, partners will deposit scientific peer-reviewed publications in a centralised repository. Generally, BioRural will conform to the EC Open Access mandates: as a minimum, all publications will be available via Green Open Access, e.g., OpenAIRE, ResearchGate and repositories supported by individual institutions and when possible, Gold Open Access will be selected, using project and own funding contributions.

BioRural will strive to publish at least 3 peer reviewed scientific papers in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project's work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners (CERTH, AU, VDU, LLU, UC, UL) and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the BioRural project.

Industry publications

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, BioRural aims to publish at least 15 featured articles in high-quality industry magazines, to make the project and its results known to the industrial stakeholders. To maximise impact, steps and timing for identifying, selecting, and producing publications have been defined:

Figure 47: BioRural steps for article submission

Important highlights until M18

During the time of submission of the deliverable, **6 articles** have been published by the BioRural partners in several local industry magazines. Some articles are showcased indicatively below:

01

La Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural arranca en España con acciones inminentes

Agentes clave en la bioeconomía llamados a participar en la Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural para transferir información y prácticas innovadoras en bioeconomía y compartir las claves para implementar y reproducir dichas innovaciones.

02

AVEBIOM participa en el II Foro de Bioeconomía Rural de Castilla y León, en octubre de 2023, donde compartirá casos de éxito, mostrará lecciones aprendidas del proyecto BRANCHES, las claves y barreras para la adopción de innovaciones y lo que aportan las redes de conocimiento e innovación como la ERBN o Intercambiom.

03

AIEL partner di Biorural, per rilanciare le aree rurali europee con la bioeconomia circolare

Le sviluppo di una vera bioeconomia è la chiave per creare un'economia europea circolare e rigenerativa, utilizzando risorse biologiche rinnovabili provenienti da colture, foreste, organismi e interagenti per produrre cibo, materiali ed energia in maniera più sostenibile e inclusiva.

04

Green Energy: România risipește resturile de lemn, în loc să încălzească satele

Figure 48: Publications in industry magazines of partners countries

Policy Guideline Report

To increase the uptake and the promotion of the currently available small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas, a comprehensive set of policy measures is required. More specifically through the success stories and the advancements of the project, the consortium aims to formulate recommendations to identify new growth opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors and foster interactions with and between EC services and other related national/international initiatives. Consulting with EC actors (i.e., DG AGRI, DG ENER, DG CLIMA, DG GROW, DG RTD, DG ENV, DG JRC) will optimise the developed Policy Guidelines and maximise their impact. Findings will be translated into 2 policy reports (one joined policy brief will be developed in collaboration with the other three projects from the same topic and one policy guideline report), increasing the share of Bioeconomy value in rural areas.

White papers

One white paper will be published to translate BioRural results into usable evidence for policy makers that draws from scientific data and stakeholder input. The publication will inform policy makers about the results and impacts of governance model adoption in view of future policy design and help shape public policy and future regulations in the field of bioeconomy.

Practice Abstracts

According to the GA, BioRural will produce 30 practice abstracts in the EIP Agri format dedicated to the project's activities and outcomes. The goal of the PAs is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/ practice regarding the deployment of biobased solutions that can be used by the end-users to enhance circular economy and bioeconomy in the rural areas. The innovative knowledge and end-user material delivered by the project will feed into the EIP-AGRI website for wider dissemination (T5.2).

Important highlights until M18

Based on the content already developed, partners have agreed to surpass the target number of 15 PAs for the first batch of Practice Abstracts (due on February 29th) and to finally include **27 PAs** related to the following themes:

- Rural current Bioeconomy status in EU and in all participating countries (15 PAs)
- Factors influencing adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions in rural areas (2 PAs)
- ERBN network (1 PA)
- BioRural Toolkit (1 PA)
- BioRural success stories (8 PAs)

The PAs will be showcased in the EIP-AGRI website as well as in the BioRural website. For publishing all PAs on the project's website and ensure homogeneity of the information provided partners, the template as presented in Figure 49 has been developed:

Figure 49: BioRural PAs template

3.2.4 Event planning

Event planning will take part in two phases. On a 6-month basis an event planning form will be sent to the partners to describe the events that are already in their calendars (Annex D). A brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for BioRural (i.e., workshop, booth) will support the decision-making process. This form has been sent and is already being used by partners. Responses are compiled using an online reporting tool (Table 7) for easy reference and record keeping.

Table 7: BioRural's event participation template

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

To better coordinate efforts between partners participating at similar events and establish an effective plan for BioRural, information will be consolidated online in a living document that will be updated frequently.

The second phase involves the selection of events. This will be done based upon the guidelines below. These necessary actions and when they should occur will ensure event participation aligns with the project objectives and budget. These will need to be adapted to individual activities, since numerous factors can result in varying steps and deadlines.

Figure 50: Guidelines for event selection and planning

3.2.5 Networking and synergies

Building synergies and expanding the BioRural ecosystem is a significant priority of the DEC plan. Much of the project's work will build upon the experience, knowledge and/or data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach will be extended to the DEC and will involve a three-step process.

Phase 1: Identification

Potentially mutually beneficial partnerships and synergies will first be identified, building from the list provided in the template in Table 8.

Table 8: BioRural's synergy & liaison mapping template

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

The template is sent to all partners requesting information on any other project's/networks or initiatives they are currently participating in that could be relevant to BioRural. This template will be revised every 6 months to add new projects.

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure synergies will benefit the project and align with BioRural's objectives, each potential project, initiatives, and network will be assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance;
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value);
- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources);
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation will be consolidated with the information provided by partners and a final decision will be made by the consortium.

Phase 3: Contact

Once it has been agreed upon that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact will be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities will be decided after discussions with their representatives and the BioRural consortium and will include (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities;
- Joint policy events;
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications;
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs;
- Participation in the other's events & networks;
- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

All the project's templates have been uploaded by FSH to the project's Google Drive folder that has been created, providing direct and continuous access to partners for updating reasons.

Important highlights until M18

Until the submission phase of the deliverable, partners have initiated partnerships with other projects. A list

of projects that have been identified as relevant to the projects is presented below:

	<p>SEEDSPRO2WINE implements one circular business model based on a pioneering & mature-R&D-results industrial process for the extraction of proteins from de-tannificated grape to be exploited as a fining agent in the wine industry and to replace the traditionally-used protein gelatin of animal origin and protein extracts from food crops. A MoA has been signed between SEEDSPRO2WINE and BioRural for awareness raising & networking activities, communication and dissemination activities, as well as development of joint project ideas around circular Bioeconomy.</p>
	<p>BBioNets will constitute a thematic network that will rely on, promote, and further advance the work carried out by EIP AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) with respect to management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs). BioRural partner IUNG presented BioRural and the toolkit during the kick off meeting of BBioNets that took place in November 2023.</p>
	<p>EOM4SOIL aims at proposing best management practices of external organic matter (EOM) pre-processing and application on soil to contribute to climate change mitigation and improve soil health. Representative farming systems in Europe (arable crops and vineyards) are selected, taking into account the diversity of pedoclimatic conditions. The net budget of soil C storage and greenhouse gas emission including the pre-process step and field application, is assessed as well as the multiple effects of EOM application on soils including contaminants are quantified. Innovative pre-processing is recommended to improve C budget and soil health. BioRural project partner AIEL participated in the event " State of the biochar supply chain in Italy" organised by the EOM4SOIL project by presenting BioRural and the toolkit. The event took place in May 2023.</p>
	<p>The Alps4GreenC project, funded by INTERREG Alpine Space, aims at setting-the-scene for transnational utilisation of biomass residues in the Alpine region, with a focus on Northern Italy, Austria, and Slovenia. The project searches biomass conversion opportunities and transnational biochar value chains. BioRural partner AIEL along with Alps4GreenC organised a workshop named after "The present and the future of biochar Innovation, regulation, and real application cases". The workshop took place in March 2023.</p>
	<p>The AgriFoodTe project aims to launch four demonstration pilots (Living Labs), which will be monitored to calculate the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of the innovative measures that are being implemented. The project has a duration of three years. BioRural partner AVEBIOM cooperated with the AgriFoodTe project for the organisation of two workshops on Inland and Biobased Industries (under T.3.2) in</p>

October 2023.

Rural Bioeconomy Alliance (RBA)

A significant update is the formation of the [Rural Bioeconomy Alliance \(RBA\)](#) with the participation of BioRural and 10 other projects. The Rural Bioeconomy Alliance is a newly established cluster of European-funded projects with a primary mission to promote the development of circular rural bioeconomy initiatives in the European Union, launched at the COOPID Bioeconomy Conference, on 31 May 2023, in Brussels.

The RBA comprises several European-funded projects, including:

1. BioRural;
2. [MainstreamBIO](#);
3. [P2Green](#);
4. [RELIEF](#);
5. [RuralBioUp](#);
6. [SCALE-UP](#);
7. [COOPID](#);
8. [BioModel4Regions](#);
9. [ShapingBio](#);
10. [CEE2ACT](#);
11. [ROBIN](#).

These projects share a common goal of developing and analysing success stories, best practices, pilots, and strategies to enhance the adoption of circular bioeconomy concepts in rural areas.

As a part of the alliance, BioRural and other members have the opportunity to share insights and knowledge on innovative technology advancements. The Alliance actively promotes information exchange on successful case studies and pilots and provides support for organising workshops and seminars. Additionally, the Rural Bioeconomy Alliance encourages collaborative presentations at high-level events and conferences, granting members access to wider and more relevant audiences. Through collaborative efforts within the Alliance, members can accelerate the development of circular rural bioeconomy initiatives across the EU, thereby contributing to a sustainable future for all. The RBA will include additional members within the coming months.

Other synergies

On the 9th of May 2023, a [Conference](#) was organised by AVEBIOM through the BioRural and BRANCHES projects with the collaboration of **more than 10 National and European innovation projects**. The conference included the organisation of a workshop dedicated to Innovative business practices that enable new businesses in bioenergy and bioeconomy, the presentation of the participating projects and the creation of synergies

as well as networking between them. A list of the participating projects and initiatives is presented below:

Project	Programme	Type
MainstreamBIO	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion

SCALE-UP	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
BIOTRANSFORM	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
ROBIN	Horizon Europe	BIOECONOMY - promotion
AGROFOSSILFREE	H2020	BIOENERGY - promotion and transfer
Biomasa CAP	INTERREG POCTEP	BIOENERGY - Promotion and transfer
AURORAL	H2020	BIOENERGY - ICT tools support
BEcoop	H2020	BIOENERGY
MOR-e	AECID	BIOENERGY
Forest Biomass in the industrial sector in Jalisco, Mexico	Private promotion	BIOENERGY
BIOCOGEN	ERDF. Portugal 2020 Programme	BIOENERGY
LIFE4DRYGAS	LIFE	BIOENERGY
ALL-TO-GAS	AEI	BIOENERGY
LDBA	ERDF-MRR	BIOENERGY
RE4Industry	H2020	BIOENERGY
Use of agricultural residues for the development of biobased materials	Private promotion	BIOPRODUCTS
LIFE Bioreformed	LIFE	BIOPRODUCTS
BeonNAT	BBI-JU	BIOPRODUCTS
BIOCISTUS 4.0	National R&D&I Plan	BIOPRODUCTS
BIOVALOR	PRTR - NextGeneration EU	BIOPRODUCTS
ESjara	PDR	BIOPRODUCTS
TREEDS	HE	FORESTRY
FIREPOCTEP	INTERREG POCTEP	FORESTRY
CHAMELEON	H2020	FORESTRY
transForm	Next Generation (Portugal)	FORESTAL

3.2.6 EC tools

BioRural will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project's result

Figure 51: EC Tools

4 Monitoring and evaluation

4.1 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are concrete, measurable targets used for monitoring and evaluating the project's progress and enabling adaptation when necessary. A set of dissemination and communication KPIs and targets have been identified and are presented in the following tables:

Table 9: Dissemination KPIs

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D1	Project events	
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5
D2	Scientific publications	
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15
D3	ERBN	
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000
D4	Synergies	
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5
D5	Policy guidelines	
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>5

Table 10: Communication KPIs

#	Communication KPIs	Target
C1	Branding & material	
C1.1	Visual identity	1
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1
C1.3	Website	1
C1.4	Social media channels	5
C1.5	Flyers	4000
C1.6	Banners	15
C2	Digital outreach	
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000
C2.2	Blog posts	60
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5

C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000
C3	Multiplier campaigns	
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500
C3.2	Press releases	9
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10

4.2 KPIs per year

Furthermore, the KPIs have been distributed between the three years in which the DEC plan will be also updated. Table 11 and 12 include a breakdown of the expected KPIs and their targets to be achieved during each year. This will be a preliminary plan that is foreseen and is subject to change and updated by each deliverable based on projections of the project activities and the scope of each partner. Furthermore, the reporting mechanism will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets.

Table 11: Dissemination KPIs per Year

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
D1	Project events				
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)	5		5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42		42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4		4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	1	7	3
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	1	3	2
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5		3	5
D2	Scientific publications				
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3			3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15		6	10
D3	ERBN				
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5			6
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5		2	5
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5			6
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1			1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000			
D4	Synergies				
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15		9	10
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4			5
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5		3	3
D5	Policy guidelines				
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1			2
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1			2

Table 12: Communication KPIs per Year

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
C1	Branding & material				
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1		
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1		
C1.3	Website	1	1		
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5		
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000		
C1.6	Banners	15	15		
C2	Digital outreach				
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	10	21	29
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	135	195	175
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	3-5	5		
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000			
C3	Multiplier campaigns				
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500			
C3.2	Press releases	9	1	4	4
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	2	9	
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	8		12
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10			10

Important highlights until M18

The first 18 months of the project were fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and was used to:

- Stakeholder Mapping: Identifying and comprehending stakeholders and their needs that demand our attention.
- Strategic Branding: Crafting the project's website, visual identity, communication materials, and dynamic social media platforms.
- Collaborative Decision-Making Protocol: Laying the groundwork for transparent event selection, publication decisions, and the identification of fruitful synergies.
- Engagement: Initiating collaborations with parallel projects and initiatives for a wider sphere of influence.
- Visible Presence: Active participation in events and dissemination via press releases and informative newsletters.
- Unified Communication: Ensuring all partners are well-versed in communication channels, templates, and protocols.

As we stride into the next reporting period, our efforts will intensify, embarking on:

- Synergy Formation: Forge strategic ties with related projects and associations, amplifying our impact and reach.
- Democratising Knowledge: Disseminating the wealth of knowledge generated within the project through the creation of comprehensive training material (T3.1).

- **Press Outreach Advancement:** Bolstering our proactive engagement in press outreach, we're set to further amplify our impact. This entails skilfully crafted press releases, captivating interviews, and insightful articles featured in pertinent magazines. Through these channels, we aim not only to disseminate project achievements to a wider audience but also to stimulate a deeper understanding of the BioRural objectives.

4.3 KPIs per partner

In order to effectively share the responsibility for spreading project results and maximising the impact derived from partners' expertise, experience, and networks, KPIs and targets have been assigned to each partner as presented in the following tables:

Table 13: Dissemination KPIs per partner

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
D1	Project events																					
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop	5	5	•			•		•	•		•		•					•	•		•
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	42	42	1	3	3	3	3		3	3	3	3	3		3	1	1		3	3	3
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops	4	4	•	•					•		•	•									
D1.4	Participation in conferences	>10	11	4						2	2	1		1					1			
D1.5	Participation in workshops	>5	6	2						1		1		1					1			
D1.6	Participation in webinars	>5	8	1	1	1				1	1	1		1					1			
D2	Scientific publications																					
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences	3	3						1	1	1											
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	>15	16			2	1						4		1	1	4			1	1	1
D3	ERBN																					
D3.1	Representation in fairs	>5	6	1	1	1							1			1						1
D3.2	Representation in working groups	>5	7	1					1	1	1	1		1					1			
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions	>5	6	1		1							1			1					1	1
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1	1														1					
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders	10000	10000																			
D4	Synergies																					
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	>15	17	4		4				2			3			2	2					
D4.2	Representation in working groups	>4	5	1		1				1			1			1						
D4.3	Representation in alliances	>5	6	2	1					1			1					1				
D5	Policy guidelines																					
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report	>1	2	2																		
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials	>1	2							1	1											

Table 14: Communication KPIs per partner

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Sum	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
C1	Branding & material																					
C1.1	Visual identity	1	1														1					
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1	1														1					
C1.3	Website	1	1														1					
C1.4	Social media channels	5	5														5					
C1.5	Flyers	4000	4000	450	200	200		200	200	300	200	300	300	200		200	450	200		200	200	200
C1.6	Banners	15	15														15					
C2	Digital outreach																					
C2.1	Unique visitors (website)	1000	0																			
C2.2	Blog posts	60	60	8	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	6	2	2	2	11	6	2	2	2	2
C2.3	Social media Posts (in all social media)	>500	505	50	20	20	20	20	20	10	20	20	30	20	20	20	85	50	20	20	20	20
C2.4	Social media audience	>1000	1100																			
C2.5	Hashtags in social media	5	5														5					
C2.6	Distributed printed/digital promotional materials	2000	2000														2000					
C3	Multiplier campaigns																					
C3.1	E-newsletter subscriptions	>500	505																			
C3.2	Press releases	9	9	1						1	1		1				2	1	2			
C3.3	Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos	11	11	1	1		1			1		1	1		1		2	1		1		
C3.4	Marketing-style videos with introduction success stories & innovators interviews	20	20	2	2		2			2		2	2		2		2	2		2		
C3.5	2 Podcast series (10 episodes) in Google podcasts app	10	10														10					

4.4 Reporting tools

Event and communication reporting

During the first months of the project, the seamless execution of timely reporting and effective monitoring for all dissemination and communication activities was of paramount importance. To facilitate this process, FSH devised an online form, exemplified below, to systematically gather input from our consortium partners. This form was designed to capture the intricacies of their undertaken measures while ensuring a streamlined reporting structure. Within this framework, partners were entrusted with the responsibility of furnishing comprehensive feedback on their dissemination and communication endeavours on a monthly basis. This practice allowed for a meticulous tracking of project progress and a real-time assessment of the alignment between planned activities and actual implementation.

The screenshot shows a Google Form with the BioRural logo at the top. The title is "BioRural Event, Activity and Communication Reporting". The text inside the form reads: "Dear BioRural partners, This form will be used for reporting all activities and events organized or attended by the BioRural consortium members as well as communication channels engaged by the consortium members on a monthly basis. You are kindly requested to fill in the relevant information prior to the monthly consortium meeting so we may update the website and social media in a timely manner. Information will also be used to track KPIs and ensure we are meeting them. Sincerely, Foodscale Hub Team".

Figure 52: Google forms for collecting partner information regarding events and communication

However, as the project evolved, the need for an even more refined and collaborative approach to KPI reporting was recognized. As a result, a transition was made from the initial online form to a more interactive and adaptable tool, constructed using Google Spreadsheets. This solution fostered enhanced communication and collaboration between partners, facilitating a more robust data exchange process for the measured outcomes. This strategic shift empowered partners to provide granular insights into their progress. This iterative process ensures that KPIs remain aligned with project objectives, ultimately contributing to more effective impact measurement and strategic decision-making. Still, each month, all partners are requested to update this online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure has proven that it reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. FSH is responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and giving updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case, significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes on the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan. In total, this online google spreadsheet has been developed and uploaded on the project's shared Drive and is available to all partners. The spreadsheet includes the following:

- **Sheet 1: Instructions** - The workbook provides instructions, a description of the KPIs, the breakdown per reporting period and a sheet dedicated to each partner. In each spreadsheet, the respective participating organisation can see the KPIs assigned to them, and the dissemination and communication activities that need to be reported, accordingly, per month of action.

Instructions

- This file has been designed to track the KPIs committed in the GA and the targets agreed upon by partners included in the DEC plan. The overall and yearly breakdown of the Dissemination & Communication KPIs can be found on the [Total KPIs sheet](#).
- Each partner has a dedicated sheet with two tables:
 - KPIs distribution**
 - The overall target for each KPI per partner
 - Dissemination & Communication actions including:**
 - Please use the drop down menu to select the category of dissemination & communication activity that your organisation organised, participated and/or executed and provide the date, name and link of the activity.
 - Please indicate if the dissemination activity should be considered a joint activity (**external to the consortium**). If yes, please indicate with whom.
- In case the dissemination/communication activity does not fall under the already existing KPI categories, do not fill in the drop-down menu and leave it empty, while filling-in all the other columns.
- Click on links for each month to upload pictures or relevant materials (e.g., agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.

Please note:

- * we suggest posts come from your organization's social media account, rather than a personal account and that you tag BioRural
- * please include the dates and links
- * blog posts refer to the creation of content included in BioRural's website (posts to other websites can be also made)

Figure 53: Instructions for the new reporting form

- **Sheet 2: KPIs per year** - This sheet includes the allocation of the KPIs per year of implementation by taking into account the implementation progress.

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Target
D1	Project events				
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)		5		5
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops		42		42
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops		4		4
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1	7	3	11
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1	3	2	6
D1.6	Participation in webinars		3	5	8
D2	Scientific publications				
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences			3	3
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines		6	10	16
D3	ERBN				
D3.1	Representation in fairs			6	6
D3.2	Representation in working groups		2	5	7
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions			6	6
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge			1	1
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders				10000
D4	Synergies				
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects		9	10	19
D4.2	Representation in working groups			5	5
D4.3	Representation in alliances		3	3	6
D5	Policy guidelines				
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report			2	2
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials			2	2

Figure 54: Total KPIs allocation per year

- **Individual Partner Reporting Sheets**

A set of distinct reporting sheets has been crafted for each consortium partner. These tailored sheets serve as a user-friendly and efficient platform for documenting their executed dissemination and communication

D5.2 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (1st update)

activities. The process has been streamlined for ease of use and accuracy. Within these sheets, a user-friendly drop-down menu is integrated under the KPI category tab. This intuitive feature empowers partners to conveniently select the relevant category for their executed dissemination or communication action. Subsequent fields facilitate the input of essential information, encompassing data specifics, activity names, associated links, and other pertinent details. To facilitate differentiation between no reporting and nonparticipation in relevant activities, partners can indicate "Nothing to report" if they have no dissemination or communication activities to report. Additionally, to support visual documentation, each month features clickable links to designated folders for partners to upload photos and other pertinent materials such as agendas, presentations, and minutes. These resources may be leveraged for reporting, dissemination, or communication purposes. This comprehensive framework ensures a holistic approach to tracking, documenting, and sharing project activities. This structured format enhances the clarity and consistency of reporting, ensuring that all vital information is accurately captured. The user-friendly design encourages partners to comprehensively document their activities, fostering an environment of collaboration and data accuracy.

October 2023									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>					
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			

November 2023									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			

December 2023									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	Communication KPI	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Please indicate "nothing to report" if needed				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			

Figure 55: Individual Partner Reporting Sheet

The form is also available on project’s google drive, enabling partners to go back and review or add missing activities and it also allows for different members from the same organisation to provide input without redundancy. FSH monitors the reporting form monthly to keep track of engagement, and on a six-month basis consolidates the results of the reporting forms and evaluates them next to the KPIs. The findings of these reports will serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies, enabling pivoting when necessary or to inform partners when additional effort is required.

4.5 Monitoring tool for KPI tracking

To precision and efficiency in monitoring the KPIs, FSH has meticulously developed and deployed a dedicated monitoring tool to track the progress of our partners' achieved KPIs. This robust tool is constructed utilising the capabilities of Google Spreadsheets, enabling real-time monitoring of KPI progress across reporting periods and partners. Figure 56 displays the comprehensive monitoring spreadsheet, where dissemination and communication KPIs are thoughtfully categorised into the three years of project implementation. Within each year, two validation statuses have been established to ensure both the timely completion of KPIs and the prompt implementation of mitigation measures, should the need arise.

D5.2 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (1st update)

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	6 month check	Final check	Status	Year 2	28/11/2023	Final check	Status	Year 3	6 month check	Final check	Status	Sum	Target	Status
D1	Project events															
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)					5	2							2	5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops					42	6							6	42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops					4	1							1	4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1		19	Complete	7	3			3				22	11	
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1		3	Complete	3	2			2				5	6	
D1.6	Participation in webinars					3	1			5				1	8	
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences									3				0	3	
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines					6				10				0	16	
D3	ERBN															
D3.1	Representation in fairs									6				0	6	
D3.2	Representation in working groups					2	1			5				1	7	
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions									6				0	6	
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge									1				0	1	
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders													0	10000	
D4	Synergies															
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects					9	1			10				1	19	
D4.2	Representation in working groups									5				0	5	
D4.3	Representation in alliances					3				3				0	6	
D5	Policy guidelines															
D5.1	Policy Guideline Report									2				0	2	
D5.2	White paper to inform national & regional government officials									2				0	2	

Figure 56: Monitoring tool for the KPIs

Moreover, within the same integrated spreadsheet file, individual sheets are thoughtfully allocated to each partner. These dedicated sheets are meticulously updated by FSH based on partners' monthly reports, consolidating their achievements and contributions. This meticulous approach further enhances transparency, collaboration, and accountability, streamlining the process of assessing our collective progress and promptly addressing any potential challenges.

#	KPI	TARGET														
Dissemination KPIs																
D1	Project events															
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops	1														
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines	4														
D3	ERBN															
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge	1														
D4	Synergies															
D4.1	Liaison with EU projects	2														
Communication KPIs																
C1	Branding & material															
C1.1	Visual identity	1														
C1.2	Motto in all project languages	1														
C1.3	Website	1														
C1.4	Social media channels	5														
C1.5	Flyers	450														
C1.6	Banners	15														

Figure 57: Monitoring tool for each partner

The current progress of the Dissemination and Communication KPIs in relation to the targets set for the initial reporting period is outlined in Figure 58. It's important to note that the current status is based on the input provided by partners through the reporting form, which may not encompass the entirety of activity engagement. In the table, the status Completed indicates the respective KPIs have been successfully achieved, reflecting the notable progress made in meeting the targets. Also, the Ongoing status signifies the KPIs that are well on track. Conversely, the red boxes highlight KPIs that require heightened attention and effort to ensure successful attainment. This comprehensive overview aids in gauging the alignment of our current progress with the predetermined targets.

#	Dissemination KPIs	Year 1	6 month check	Final check	Status	Year 2	28/11/2023	Final check	Status	Year 3	6 month check	Final check	Status	Sum	Target	Status
D1	Project events															
D1.1	Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshop (one per Bioeconomy theme)					5	2							2	5	
D1.2	Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops					42	6							6	42	
D1.3	Organisation of RBP workshops					4	1							1	4	
D1.4	Participation in conferences	1		19	Completed	7	3			3				22	11	
D1.5	Participation in workshops	1		3	Completed	3	2			2				5	6	
D1.6	Participation in webinars					3	1			5				1	8	
D2	Scientific publications															
D2.1	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences									3				0	3	
D2.2	Articles in industry magazines					6				10				0	16	
D3	ERBN															
D3.1	Representation in fairs									6				0	6	
D3.2	Representation in working groups					2	1			5				1	7	
D3.3	Representation in exhibitions									6				0	6	
D3.4	Organization of the European Bioeconomy Challenge									1				0	1	
D3.5	Engagement of stakeholders													0	10000	

Figure 58: Completed, Ongoing and Uncompleted Dissemination KPIs

KPIs tracking until M18

Many of the KPI targets that have been set until month 18 have been met already or exceeded. Certain KPIs have even reached and exceeded the target number for M36. For KPI targets that have not been met specific action points have been identified. More specifically:

KPIs that are achieved or exceeded – Dissemination KPIs

- **D1.4 Participation in conferences (target until M18: 8, target until M36: 11)**
The participation of partners to conferences has exceeded the total target number reaching the number of **20**.
- **D1.5 Participation in workshops (target until M18: 4, target until M36: 6)**
The participation of partners to workshops to workshops has exceeded the total target number reaching the number of **10**.
- **D1.6 Participation in webinars (target until M18: 3, target until M36: 8)**
The participation of partners to webinars has exceeded the target number for M18 by reaching the number of **4**.
- **D2.2 Articles in industry magazines (target until M18: 6, target until M36: 16)**
Partners have published **6** articles in industry magazines achieved the target number for M18.
- **D3.1 Representation in fairs (target until M18: 0, target until M36: 6)**
Although no representations in fairs have been predicted for M18, the number of representations exceeded the target for M36 reaching the number of **10**.
- **D3.2 Representation in working groups (target until M18: 2, target until M36: 7)**
The representation of partners in working groups has exceeded the target number for M18 reaching the number of **5**.
- **D3.3 Representation in exhibitions (target until M18: 0, target until M36: 6)**
Although no representations in exhibitions have been predicted for M18, the number of representations has already reached the number of **3**.
- **D4.2 Representation in working groups (target until M18: 0, target until M36: 5)**
Although no representations in exhibitions have been predicted for M18, the number of representations has already reached the number of **4**.
- **D4.3 Representation in alliances (target until M18: 3, target until M36: 6)**
The representation in alliances has achieved the target number for M18.

KPIs that are achieved or exceeded – Communication KPIs

- KPIs **C1.1 Visual identity (1)**, **C1.2 Motto in all project languages (1)**, **C1.3 Website (1)**, **C1.4 Social media channels (5)**, **C1.6 Banners (15)**, **C2.5 Hashtags in social media (5)** have been achieved.
- **C2.1 Unique visitors (website)** has exceeded the target number for M36 (1000) reaching the number of **2.100** already.

KPIs that are on track

- Dissemination KPIs **D1.1 Organisation of online knowledge exchange workshops** (one per Bioeconomy theme), **D1.2 Organisation of physical national capacity building workshops**, **D1.3 Organisation of RBP workshops** are on track following the implementation pace of the relative tasks (T3.1, T3.2 & T3.3).
- **C2.3 Social media Posts (in all social media) (target number until M18: 190, target number until M36: 505)**

Partners have been asked to make new posts and share the posts made from BioRural social media accounts. The posts have to be made from the institutional social media accounts of the partners (number of posts made so far 185).

KPIs Requiring Additional Attention

- **D2.1 Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences (target number until M36:3)**

Although this KPI has been allocated to the 3rd year of the project implementation, partners have been asked to plan their publications.

- **C2.2 Blog posts (target number until M18:20, target number until M36: 60)**

Partners have been asked to provide content for the development of blog posts circulated via the project website (number of blog posts made 19). The content of the blog posts can relate to the BioRural objectives or directly with the partners progress and implementation of activities.

- **C3.1 E-newsletter subscriptions (target number until M36: 505)**

The achieved number of subscriptions until M18 is 147. Partners have been requested to promote the newsletter subscription in all events as well as include it in the institutional newsletters. Participants in the training activities under WP3 are also invited to subscribe.

- **C3.3 Interviews in radio/TV & outreach videos (target number until M36: 11)**

Partners have been asked to plan and deliver the interview and/or radio and TV outreach videos.

5 Exploitation & IPR management

BioRural will produce several commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This chapter provides a presentation of these results, potential pathways for their exploitation and IPRs related to them as identified until M3. Further analysis on the Exploitation strategy will be developed by M18 with D5.2 and M36 with D5.3 to expand upon this initial plan and provide a concrete roadmap for the duration of the project and beyond.

5.1 Exploitation pathways

Each KER requires a unique exploitation approach based upon the type and whether it can be commercialised. A description of the KERs, their target groups and the unique value they offer are described in this section as well as potential exploitation pathways for commercial and non-commercial results.

BioRural has identified 4 key exploitable results (KERs) that will be available for use/reuse by partners and target groups stakeholders. Tables 15-18 describe each result, scope of exploitation, UVP, target groups and scope/ means of exploitation.

All partners provided their feedback by answering an online table - tailor made to BioRural's exploitation and IPR validation (Annex I).

The following table presents the KERs associated with the partners involved in their exploitation according to the identification process made during DEC preparation.

Table 15: ERBN- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: European Rural Bioeconomy Network	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Four regional RBPs will be formed by splitting Europe in 4 quartiles (NW, NE, SW and SE) to connect neighbouring countries and identify commonalities to impose members' connection and ensure sustainability. The 4 RBPs will constitute the ERBN. All partners will locate, make connections, and develop synergies with Bioeconomy actors to stimulate knowledge exchange, cooperation and collaboration and assist in developing future rural Bioeconomy initiatives. Each RBP will be led by one partner (NW: DELPHY, NE: IUNG, SW: AVE and SE: CERTH) to ensure the process continuation during the project.
Unique Value Proposition	Creation of a Network of more than 400 members from various sectors including primary sector, Academia, Public Authorities, Industry, Consultants etc. joining forces to boost Bioeconomy in rural areas.
Target groups	Scientific Community, Policy makers, Industry, Society-Citizens, NGOs, environmental groups, think tanks, any other key actor in knowledge transfer" (or any key actor in the national AKIS system)
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial & Commercial

<p>Means of exploitation</p>	<p><u>Non-commercial</u></p> <p>The exploitation will derive from the diffusion of knowledge. The ERBN members will be invited to participate in national and regional workshops on knowledge exchange and capacity building (WP3) aimed at directly supporting them in developing and scaling rural bio-based solutions.</p> <p>Scientific exploitation is based on the diffusion of hands-on knowledge on Bioeconomy applications and solutions circulated within the scientific community that will participate in the ERBN. The scientific community can exploit the outcomes and the collected data for further research advancements in the Bioeconomy domain.</p> <p>Policy making exploitation is based on policy recommendations and increased awareness on Bioeconomy development and support interaction of policy makers from different countries and rural areas.</p>
	<p><u>Commercial exploitation</u></p> <p>The network will facilitate collaboration between stakeholders (for instance primary producers and processors) through providing them with a platform to initiate contact and sharing of information.</p>

European Rural Bioeconomy Network - Achievement until M18

The creation of a sustained European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN) has been discussed during the first year of the BioRural project. The network objective will be to facilitate the knowledge exchange and the interaction, to promote enhanced adoption of small-scale bio-based solutions applicable in rural areas.

At Month M18 of BioRural, the BioRural toolkit has already registered a community of interest of 295 persons, representing science, technology providers, AKIS and practitioners. Many of them are not just individuals or targeted actors of BioRural. Among them several have the profile of Key actors, as being crucial to support the creation of the initial structure of the ERBN.

At M18 the potential value of the ERBN has been identified, based on the BioRural community of interest and the material available through the toolkit. It is evidenced that the challenge is to engage (based on the potential value of ERBN) a group of key actors taking the responsibility of managing, and actively organising actions of interest after project ends. Following the BioRural legat, it has been identified that the ERBN would work more naturally as thematic, instead of as regional clusters. It is necessary to have a plan to gather resources to sustain the ERBN right after the completion of BioRural.

By Month M18 all partners have identified the potential key actors in their country who could be invited and involved in the management of the ERBN. The current work consists of performing a rapprochement with these key actors in each country and understanding their interests and the value proposition to become part of ERBN management core. Once established, these key actors together with BioRural partners will discuss the ERBN functions and strategy.

Table 16: Toolkit- Key Exploitable Result

KER name: BioRural Toolkit	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	The Toolkit will integrate various levels of information (e.g., scientific publications & reports, policy guidelines, legislation) and make it available to small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.
Unique Value Proposition	An effective, all-encompassing BioRural Toolkit with an enhanced repository of up-to-date Bioeconomy data.
Target groups	Innovators, Rural areas' actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial

<p>Means of exploitation</p>	<p>The exploitation of the KER will derive from the diffusion of knowledge related to various sources such as scientific papers and reports, research projects, policy guidelines, legislation and financing or in-kind initiatives related to bio-based solutions for rural areas.</p> <p>Scientific exploitation is related to the scientific and research papers that will be available within the Toolkit. Scientific community can exploit the outcomes and the collected data for further research advancements in the Bioeconomy domain. Examples from the project include two types of questionnaires (for end-users and experts) for identifying stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests; the data on structural characteristics of rural small businesses population that will participate in the systematic end-users survey; and national and regional (across four RBP) findings from the survey providing an overview of stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests about bio-based solutions for rural areas. The country factsheets to be created under T1.1 and findings from the survey will provide an overview of stakeholders' needs, innovative ideas and interests about bio-based solutions for rural areas.</p> <p>Policy making exploitation is related to the availability of policy recommendations & white papers within the Toolkit. EU, regional and national policy makers can utilise the project's data and results (that will be also deposited to the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy), enhancing the development of evidence-based Bioeconomy policies.</p> <p>Training exploitation is related to the training material & video tutorials of the online Bioeconomy workshops, that will be available within the Toolkit to citizens, NGOs and other interested groups.</p>
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Toolkit - Progress Achievement

BioRural toolkit will enable networking of stakeholders, knowledge sharing of bioeconomy as well as business models, and will support post-project sustainability.

The BioRural toolkit have **363 registered members**. Those stakeholders represent: Private company/self-employed (132 members), Associations, clusters, NGOs (113 members), Research and education (113 members), Government and public administrations (20 members), Other (26 members). They are interested in themes regarding Bioenergy (208 members), Forestry/natural habitat (125 members), Food/agriculture (246 members), Biomaterials (144 members), Aquatic/water systems (80 members).

Table 17: Business models - Key Exploitable Result

<p>KER name: Bio-based business models</p>	
<p>Partners contributing to its development</p>	<p>All partners</p>
<p>Description of the KER</p>	<p>Business model blueprints for each of the 5 selected Bioeconomy themes will be developed in order to support the development of successful bio-economy businesses for future innovative bio-based rural regions. The final</p>
	<p>outcome will be a highly reusable set of tools and methods that can accelerate the adoption of circular business models in rural communities in a tangible way.</p>
<p>Unique Value Proposition</p>	<p>Tailored to the Bioeconomy domain business models, designed to match the specific needs of rural stakeholders, while incorporating critical technology, business and societal aspects.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>	<p>Innovators, Rural areas' actors (e.g., farmers, foresters), Policy makers at EU, national, regional, local level</p>

Scope of exploitation	Commercial
Means of exploitation	<p>The business model blueprints will be publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit and will assist stakeholders in forming their individual circular business models with the support of the business experts of the consortium.</p> <p>Commercial exploitation: The blueprints will allow stakeholders to produce either regional Bioeconomy development models with emphasis on the specific bio-based solutions suitable for the local environment or private business plans for new ideas (from inception) and existing solutions (at any stage) that require a Bioeconomy upgrade.</p>

According to the GA, the bio-based business models will be delivered on M34.

Table 18: Policy Guidelines - Key Exploitable Result

KER name: Policy Guidelines	
Partners contributing to its development	All partners
Description of the KER	Guidelines on: (i) interactive and multi-actor innovation processes specific to bio-based solutions for rural areas; (ii) new funding formats enhancing innovation-driven research about bio-based solutions; (iii) future research; (iv) topics of interest for the national and EU research agendas (including further HE programming); (v) fostering a better targeted and shared research agenda on innovation-driven research and multi-actor projects.
Unique Value Proposition	Supporting Bioeconomy development, considering the selected themes and involved regions' specificities. Legislative barriers will be mitigated by developing policy guidelines that feedback into the development of the circular rural Bioeconomy.
Target groups	Policy makers, National & regional government officials
Scope of exploitation	Non-commercial
Means of exploitation	<p>The policy guidelines will be publicly available through the BioRural Toolkit as well as via Zenodo that will be uploaded upon their completion.</p> <p>Policy making exploitation: Policy guidelines will consist of research and policy recommendations and produce crisp and focused policy briefs with key messages easily and quickly grasped by the target groups. EU, regional and national policy makers can utilise the project's policy guidelines, enhancing the development of evidence-based Bioeconomy policies.</p>

According to the GA, the Policy guidelines will be delivered on M24.

Table 19: Identified KERs & involved partners

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Partners involved in KERs exploitation																		
		P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16	P17	P18	P19
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Toolkit	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3	Business model blueprints	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
4	Policy Guidelines	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓					✓			

All BioRural’s currently identified KERs will be openly accessible and available free of charge during the project’s lifetime. After the project’s completion the BioRural Toolkit and ERBN will be further developed by all partners ensuring the reuse of assets by the Bioeconomy community.

In particular, the further development of the **BioRural Toolkit** and enrichment with relevant Bioeconomy data including scientific research, projects and initiatives, success stories and funding opportunities, will be undertaken mainly by the scientific partners. In this light, it will become freely and openly available through a vast network of relevant stakeholders and the general public. The benefits are twofold:

- ensure that key stakeholders and end-users have continuous access to the platform and its innovative tools.
- get immediate access to new validated data that will continuously populate the Toolkit.

The post project sustainability of the **BioRural network** beyond EC funding will be addressed thoroughly in a comprehensive **Sustainability plan (D5.3 in M36)** that will address the following key aspects of network’s modus operandi, namely:

- Institutional plan:** will cover the legal form, the governance model of the network, the decision-making process, and the conditions for membership. The governance model will be designed under the principles of inclusiveness, openness and expansion;
- Organisational plan:** will define the internal structure of the network, roles, responsibilities, and job descriptions. It will be designed under the principles of efficiency, cost-effectiveness and will aim to support the scale-up potential of the network;
- Financial plan:** will set-up the basis of a dual purpose, sustainability in terms of covering the operational costs of the network and affordability so that rural communities and stakeholders can become members and benefit from network services. While the detailed financial model will be defined in WP5 during project implementation, the basic principle of the financial model will be as follows: Stakeholders that are interested in the services of the Toolkit can become members by subscribing and paying an annual membership fee (with minimum possible pricing). Membership fee will be substantial enough to cover the costs associated with the maintenance of the platform, but at the same time very affordable to the members, even in low-income European countries.

Identification of new KERs- project procedure

As the project progresses additional KERs might be identified by the partners. To this end, certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in the figure below:

Figure 59: Newly identified KERs procedure

The first step towards the identification of a KER by a partner, is for the latter to inform the Coordinator and WP5 leader providing a detailed explanation of the exploitability potential of the identified result by making sure it aligns with the project exploitation plan. Specific analysis needs to be made covering the following aspects:

- Scope of exploitation
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation (how)

A relevant form has been developed and shared with the partners during DEC preparation (Annex I).

Once this step is concluded, the above-mentioned form is sent to the consortium and partners are asked to validate the new KER. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new KER is validated, it is included in the project's KERs list mentioned in Table 23.

5.2 IPR strategy

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are the ownership rights for creations of the mind, such as inventions, names, images, or designs and can enable owners to obtain financial benefit from their ideas. Striking the right balance between creator and public interests can foster creativity and innovation.

All KERs are potentially subject to IPR management. D5.7 Bio-Rural network sustainability plan will provide a detailed plan for each result and outline concrete IPR measures to be taken by the partners. BioRural will examine the protection of any result that could potentially be commercially or industrially exploited, and if possible, reasonable, and justified, protect them.

5.2.1 Types of IPR⁵

The standard forms of IPR protection include:

⁵ World Intellectual Property Organization. "What is Intellectual Property?" <https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>.

- **Patent:** an exclusive right granted for an invention. It allows the owner to decide how and whether the invention can be used by others
- **Trademark:** a sign that distinguishes goods and services of one enterprise from those of another
- **Industrial design:** includes the aesthetic aspect of an object. 2D features can include patterns, lines, and colours, whereas 3D features extend to shape and surface
- **Copyright:** is the legal term to describe the rights over literary and artistic work but can also extend to databases, advertisement, maps, and technical drawings
- **Trade-secret:** commercially valuable confidential information which may be sold or licensed. This can include technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, lists of customers
- **Confidentiality:** information that is not publicly known and warrants protection

The choice of the most suitable form will be based upon the specifications of the activity and its results.

BioRural will produce significant research results and technological innovations. Hence, a strategy that will handle all IP rights matters will be developed, creating an encouraging environment for further exploitation of the generated discoveries and knowledge. As such, BioRural handles IPR Management on a two-level approach:

During the project: BioRural will give emphasis to the protection of IPRs derived from the project implementation, ensuring that any IPR generated shall rest with the industry that created it and can further exploit it commercially. Under this framework, a set of both protective and supportive measures (such as the obligation to sign Non-Disclosure Agreements) will be undertaken by the consortium to create confidence in all participants. Knowledge Management and democratisation of scientific knowledge: The consortium will publish the overall project results through publications, seminars and in the project website, without charging intellectual property rights. Further, partners will deposit scientific peer reviewed publications in a centralised repository (Open Research Europe) as mandated by the HE “Open science policy”.

Post-Project IPR Strategy: The pre-identified and newly generated IPRs can and will be protected. However, given that BioRural is aiming to support the rural areas, the BioRural Toolkit will be licenced under a copyleft licence (e.g., GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use, and encouraging further knowledge sharing.

The following table presents the IPRs of the four KERs as they were identified by the partners during DEC preparation.

Table 20: BioRural KERs & linked IPRs

KERs		Linked IPRs to the KERs
1	European Rural Bioeconomy Network	no IPR
2	Toolkit	Copyleft
3	Business model blueprints	no IPR
4	Policy Guidelines	no IPR

Identification of new IPRs- project procedure

As the project progresses additional IPRs might be identified by the partners. To this end, a certain procedure and steps have been designed and presented in the figure below:

Figure 60: Newly identified IPRs procedure

The identification of new IPRs is closely related to the identification process of KERs described above. In that way, when a new KER is identified, the partner follows the same procedure by informing the Coordinator and the WP5 leader on the relative IPR that is linked to the KER as presented in Annex I.

Following, the partners are asked to validate the new IPR. Comments and suggestions of the partners are recorded while possible objections are discussed and addressed. Finally, after the new IPR is validated, it is included in the project’s IPR list.

5.2.2 Partner obligations

BioRural will follow all IPR management requirements described in the Grant Agreement as well as the signed Consortium Agreement.

Access rights

The beneficiaries must give each other, and the other participants access to the background identified as needed for implementing the action, subject to any specific rules in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

‘Background’ means any **data, know-how or information** — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that is:

- held by the beneficiaries before they acceded to the Agreement and
- needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Grant Agreement.

According to the Consortium Agreement and specifically Article 9, the Parties have identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and have also, where relevant, informed each other that Access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

Results and ownership

‘Results’ means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.2 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities including but not limited to research contracts in national and European funded projects with third parties provided it does not lead to any commercial or monetary benefit to third parties involved in such cooperative research project on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licences to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

The **granting authority** has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries (notably summaries for publication, deliverables, as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material, in paper or electronic form) for policy, information, communication, dissemination and publicity purposes —during the action or afterwards.

The right to use the beneficiaries' materials, documents and information is granted in the form of a royalty-free, non-exclusive, and irrevocable licence, which includes the following rights:

- i. use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the granting authority or any other EU service (including institutions, bodies, offices, agencies, etc.) or EU Member State institution or body; copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers; and communication through press information services)
- ii. distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display, or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes)
- iii. editing or redrafting (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (e.g., meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g., audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation)
- iv. translation
- v. storage in paper, electronic or other form
- vi. archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- vii. the right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license to third parties the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f), if needed for the information, communication and publicity activity of the granting authority

If materials or documents are subject to moral rights or third-party rights (including intellectual property rights or rights of natural persons on their image and voice), the beneficiaries must ensure that they comply with their obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary licences and authorisations from the rights holders concerned).

The Sustainability plan (D5.3) will include a Results ownership list as per the periodic reporting requirements of the Grant Agreement.

Transfer of results

According to the Consortium Agreement, each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results, including its share in jointly owned Results, following the procedures outlined in the Grant Agreement.

In the case of ownership transfer to the third party, the third party must be identified in Attachment (3) of the Consortium Agreement and the other Parties must waive their right to prior notice and to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement.

The transferring Party must inform the other Parties at the time of transfer and will ensure the rights of other Parties are not affected by such a transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after signing the Consortium Agreement requires a decision of the General Assembly.

Access Rights to Results

Access Rights to Results if needed for exploitation of a Party's own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement.

A request for Access Rights may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project.

For the avoidance of doubt any grant of Access Rights not covered by the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement shall be at the absolute discretion of the owning Party and subject to such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the owning and receiving Parties.

Dissemination of Results

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of partner's own results such as publications and presentations, shall be governed by the Grant Agreement.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice.

If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

An objection is justified if the intended publication:

- a) would prevent patenting or other protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background with registrable intellectual property rights or
- b) includes Background, unpublished solely owned Results or Confidential Information of the objecting Party. The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

In addition, the unpublished results or background of any partner will not be used for dissemination purposes without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval.

Access rights for software adhere to the same rules as described above. Access rights do not include source or object code ported to a certain hardware platform or software documentation beyond what is available from the party granting the access rights. The **BioRural Toolkit** will be licensed under a copyleft licence (e.g., GPLv3, AGPL), mandating the open distribution of the source code, ensuring freedom of use, and encouraging further knowledge sharing.

Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary **breaches any of the obligations** of the Grant Agreement (Section 2), the **grant may be reduced**.

Non-disclosure of information

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to any other Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally and has

been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipients hereby undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on non-disclosure under the Grant Agreement, for a period of 5 years after the end of the Project:

- a) not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- b) not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
- c) to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- d) to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

5.2.3 Next steps

At the proposal stage, the **BioRural Toolkit** was identified as a result subject to IPR. As its development progresses a thorough assessment will be undertaken to apply the most appropriate IPR. All newly generated knowledge and results will be recorded and assessed to clearly **determine ownership** and steps will be recommended for seeking proper protection. FSH will offer partners IPR support over the course of the project (M18, M30) through workshops that will provide information on the basics of IPR, rules to consider and the process to seek protection. Detailed consultation services will not be provided, as IPR protection requires legal expertise.

6 Conclusion

The Plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities (D5.2), due in M18, is an updated version of the DEC plan (D5.1). It evaluates the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions until M18 until the third iteration (M36). The final update (D5.3) “Results of the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities” will focus on the diffusion of the information and knowledge generated by the creation of the ERBN and the 4 RBNs as well as by the development of the BioRural Toolkit.

More specifically, the present document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) conducted to meet the dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners are actively involved in the communication and dissemination of BioRural aiming to assure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximise the impact.

Annex A: Logo variations

Annex B: BioRural's covers

Annex C: Dissemination and Communication material

BioRural brochure: English version and translations in partners' languages

Brochure sides A&B [English]

Expected results

- 1 European Rural Bioeconomy Network
- 4 Regional Bioeconomy Platforms
- 20 Rural Bioeconomy Success Stories
- 42 Capacity building workshops
- 4 Regional workshops
- 1 European Bioeconomy Challenge

- 440 Interviews with end users/experts
- 5 Knowledge exchange workshops
- 5 Bioeconomy business models
- Policy recommendations

- >400 Bioeconomy material
- Filmed workshops
- 8 Success stories videos
- Integration with EU's knowledge centre for Bioeconomy

Register to BioRural's Bioeconomy platform to join European BioEconomy networks!

bioruraleu

[in biorural](https://www.linkedin.com/company/biorural) [@bio_rural](https://twitter.com/bio_rural)
[f bioruraleu](https://www.facebook.com/bioruraleu) [BioRural](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBioRural)
[BioRural channel](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBioRural)

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Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Connecting the dots to

UNLOCK THE POTENTIAL

of European rural areas

towards circular BIOECONOMY

A Horizon Europe Project
1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025

Funded by the European Union

Introduction

"The bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials and energy" (EC) and a thriving bioeconomy is key to creating a circular European economy

Challenges

- Our economies are based on linear production systems using non-renewable resources
- Rural areas face acute demographic, poverty and climate challenges
- Rural bioeconomy knowledge and technology transfer is not adequately supported

...but opportunities exist

- Circular Bioeconomy solutions and networks exist
- Increased policy, research and innovation support for a circular Bioeconomy
- New bio-based innovations are consistently supporting the transition to a circular economy

Objective

"BioRural's goal is to create a European Rural Bioeconomy Network to promote small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas and to increase the share of the Bioeconomy"

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate the current status of the European Bioeconomy
- Identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions
- Create a European rural Bioeconomy network
- Assess and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building for the rural Bioeconomy
- Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool (BioRural Toolkit)
- Create rural development blueprints for Bioeconomy businesses from conception to scale

Approach

BioRural is centered on three pillars that feed into a publicly available BioRural Toolkit

Pillars

Pillar 1: Knowledge

- Information gap analysis
- Knowledge exchange workshops
- BioRural Toolkit

Pillar 2: Network

- 4 regional Rural Bioeconomy Platforms
- Circular success stories
- Synergies with previous and ongoing innovative bio-economy projects
- Capacity building and regional workshops, Bioeconomy challenge

Pillar 3: Business Models

- Business model blueprints for each theme
- Post-project sustainability

Brochure sides A&B [French]

Résultats attendus

- 1 Réseau européen de la bioéconomie
- 4 Plateformes suivant un découpage par zone géographique européennes
- 20 études de cas mise en ligne de bioéconomie rurale
- 42 Ateliers de renforcement des capacités
- 4 Ateliers à échelle de zone
- 1 Événement européen avec challenge sur la bioéconomie
- 440 Interviews d'utilisateurs/experts
- 5 Ateliers d'échanges de connaissances
- 5 Business Models pour la bioéconomie
- Recommandations politiques
- +400 Ressources sur la bioéconomie
- Ateliers enregistrés
- 8 Success Story vidéos
- Intégration avec le centre de connaissances de l'UE sur la bioéconomie

biorural.eu

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Accélérer la mise en place de solutions circulaires et biosourcées au sein des zones rurales européennes

Connecter les acteurs pour

LIBÉRER LE POTENTIEL

des zones rurales européennes vers la

BIOÉCONOMIE CIRCULAIRE

Un projet Horizon Europe
1^{er} Septembre 2022 – 31 Août 2025

Funded by the European Union

Introduction

La bioéconomie consiste à utiliser des ressources biologiques, renouvelables, comme les cultures, les forêts, les poissons, les animaux et les micro-organismes, pour produire des aliments, des matériaux et de l'énergie* (CE) et une bioéconomie prospère est essentielle à la création d'une économie européenne circulaire.

Économie circulaire au sens large (entrée, sortie, consommation)

Industries et services biosourcés

Bioénergie Biomatériaux

Matière première biologique

Sylviculture, alimentation et agriculture, eau

Innovations biosourcées

Challenges

- Nos économies sont fondées sur des systèmes de production linéaires utilisant des ressources non renouvelables
- Les zones rurales sont confrontées à de graves changements démographiques, de pauvreté et climatiques
- Les connaissances de la bioéconomie rurale et le transfert de technologies ne sont pas soutenus de manière adéquate

...mais des opportunités existent

- Des solutions de bioéconomie circulaires et des réseaux existent
- Un soutien accru aux politiques, à la recherche et à l'innovation pour une bioéconomie circulaire
- De nouvelles innovations biosourcées soutiennent en permanence la transition vers une économie circulaire

Objectifs

"L'objectif du projet BioRural est de créer un réseau paneuropéen de bioéconomie rurale afin de promouvoir des solutions biosourcées à petite échelle dans les zones rurales et d'accroître la part de la bioéconomie."

Réseau européen de la bioéconomie rurale

Nord-Ouest: Pays-Bas, France, Allemagne, Danemark

Nord-Est: Pologne, Lituanie, Lettonie

Sud-Ouest: Espagne, Portugal, Italie

Sud-Est: Grèce, Slovaquie, Macédoine du Nord, Roumanie

Objectifs spécifiques

- Évaluer le statut actuel de la bioéconomie européenne
- Identifier les facteurs affectant l'adoption et la diffusion des solutions biosourcées
- Créer un réseau européen de la bioéconomie rurale
- Faciliter l'échange de connaissances et le renforcement des capacités pour la bioéconomie rurale
- Développer et optimiser continuellement un outil en ligne ouvert aux parties prenantes
- Créer des plans de développement ruraux pour les entreprises de la bioéconomie, de la conception à la mise à l'échelle

Approche

Le projet BioRural repose sur une boîte à outils qui se décline en 3 piliers

Connaissance

Réseautage

Business Models

Piliers

Pilier 1: Connaissance

- Analyse des lacunes en matière d'information
- Ateliers d'échange de connaissances
- Boîte à outils BioRural

Pilier 2: Réseautage

- 4 plateformes régionales de bioéconomie
- Success Stories
- Synergies avec les projets de bioéconomie innovants précédents et en cours
- Renforcement des capacités et ateliers régionaux, défi de la bioéconomie

Pilier 3: Business Models

- Business Models pour chaque thématique
- Durabilité post-projet

Brochure sides A&B [Italian]

Risultati attesi

- 1 Network europeo per la bioeconomia
- 4 piattaforme regionali
- 20 Casi reali virtuosi, documentati e condivisi
- 42 workshop di formazione e condivisione
- 4 Workshop internazionali nelle macro-aree
- 1 Contest europeo per start-up e innovazioni

- 440 Interviste con utenti ed esperti
- 5 workshop di condivisione delle informazioni
- 5 modelli di business raccomandazioni ai legislatori

>400 contenuti informativi e video

- 8 video di storie di successo

Integrazione con l'EU's knowledge centre for Bioeconomy

Stimolare l'integrazione delle soluzioni bio-based nell'economia circolare delle aree rurali europee

Creare le condizioni per **RIMUOVERE GLI OSTACOLI** Allo sviluppo sostenibile della **BIOECONOMIA** Nelle aree rurali europee

➔ Registrati alla piattaforma BioRural per iscriverti al network!

in biorural

f biorural.eu

yt BioRural channel

biorural.eu

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Progetto Horizon Europe
1 settembre 2022 - 31 agosto 2025

Finanziato dall'Unione europea

Introduzione

"Economia che usa le risorse biologiche rinnovabili di prima e di seconda generazione, provenienti dalla terra e dal mare come materiale per la produzione energetica, industriale, alimentare e mangimistica" (CE) e un sistema di valorizzazione delle risorse biologiche in salute è la chiave per consentire lo sviluppo dell'economia circolare in Europa.

Sfide

- La nostra economia si basa su modelli lineari di utilizzo di risorse non rinnovabili
- Le aree rurali devono confrontarsi con povertà, spopolamento e cambiamenti climatici
- Il trasferimento delle conoscenze e delle tecnologie, in ambito bio-based, è lento e complesso

...ma esistono delle opportunità

- Le **soluzioni tecnologiche** e i modelli sono spesso già state sviluppate
- Le **politiche, la ricerca e l'innovazione** sono fortemente indirizzate verso un'economia circolare
- Le moderne soluzioni **bio-based** offrono anche un vantaggio nella transizione verso un'economia circolare

Obiettivi

"L'obiettivo di BioRural è quello di creare un network europeo che promuova soluzioni per la valorizzazione della bioeconomia su piccola scala, per far crescere il ruolo della bioeconomia nelle aree rurali"

Obiettivi specifici

- Valutare lo stato attuale della bioeconomia in Europa
- Identificare i fattori che influenzano l'adozione e la diffusione della bioeconomia nelle aree rurali
- Facilitare la condivisione delle conoscenze e la formazione per creare le professionalità nelle aree rurali
- Sviluppo e ottimizzazione di una piattaforma online per gli stakeholder
- Creazione di progetti di business per la bioeconomia dall'ideazione all'applicazione reale

Approccio

BioRural si focalizza su 3 pilastri che convergono in uno strumento gratuito: il BioRural Toolkit

Pilastri

Pilastro 1: Informazioni

- Analisi delle lacune
- Organizzazione di workshop informativi
- BioRural Toolkit

Pilastro 2: Network

- 4 piattaforme regionali
- Casi virtuosi di bioeconomia circolare
- Sinergie con progetti, focalizzati su innovazioni nella bioeconomia, conclusi e in corso
- Formazione, workshop territoriali e contest europeo

Pilastro 3: Business models

- Progetti di modelli reali per i principali temi della bioeconomia
- Valutazione della sostenibilità post-progetto

Brochure sides A&B [Portuguese]

Resultados esperados

- 1 Rede Europeia de Bioeconomia Rural
- 4 Plataformas Regionais de Bioeconomia
- 20 Histórias de Sucesso sobre Bioeconomia Rural
- 42 Ações de formação
- 4 Workshops regionais
- 1 Concurso Europeu de Bioeconomia

- 440 Entrevistas com potenciais beneficiários / especialistas
- 5 Ações de divulgação
- 5 Modelos de negócios na área da Bioeconomia
- Recomendações de políticas
- >400 materiais sobre Bioeconomia
- Ações de formação gravadas
- 8 vídeos de histórias de sucesso
- Integração com os centros de conhecimento da UE na área da Bioeconomia

Registre-se na Plataforma do Biorural para aderir às Redes Europeias de Bioeconomia!

biorural.eu

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Apoiando a integração de soluções circulares de base biotecnológica nas áreas rurais da Europa

Ligando os pontos para **DESBLOQUEAR O POTENCIAL** das zonas rurais da Europa rumo à **BIOECONOMIA CIRCULAR**

Um projeto Horizonte Europa
1 de setembro de 2022 - 31 de agosto de 2025

Financiado pela União Europeia

Introdução

"A bioeconomia significa usar recursos biológicos renováveis, como colheitas, florestas, peixes, animais e microrganismos para produzir alimentos, materiais e energia" e uma bioeconomia próspera é a chave para criar uma economia circular na Europa

Desafios

- Nossas economias são baseadas em sistemas de produção lineares usando recursos não renováveis
- As zonas rurais enfrentam graves desafios demográficos, de pobreza e climáticos
- Conhecimento da bioeconomia rural e a transferência de tecnologia não são adequadamente apoiados

...Mas as oportunidades existem

- Existem **soluções e redes de Bioeconomia Circular**
- Maior apoio a **políticas, pesquisa e inovação** para uma Bioeconomia circular
- Novas **inovações de base biológica** estão apoiando consistentemente a transição para uma economia circular

Objetivo

"O objetivo da BioRural é criar uma Rede Europeia de Bioeconomia Rural para promover soluções de base biológica de pequena escala em áreas rurais e expandir o mercado da Bioeconomia"

Specific Objectives

- Evaluate the current status of the European Bioeconomy
- Identify factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of bio-based solutions
- Create a European rural Bioeconomy network
- Assess and promote bio-based solutions in rural areas
- Facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building for the rural Bioeconomy
- Develop and continuously optimise an online open stakeholders' tool (BioRural Toolkit)
- Create rural development blueprints for Bioeconomy businesses from conception to scale

Metodologia

O BioRural está apoiado em três pilares que suportam o Conjunto de Ferramentas BioRural, disponível para utilização pública de forma aberta

Pilares

Pilar 1: Conhecimento

- Análise de lacunas de informação
- Ações de divulgação
- Conjunto de Ferramentas BioRural

Pilar 2: Rede de Partilha

- 4 Plataformas Regionais de Bioeconomia Rural
- Histórias de sucesso sobre economia circular
- Sinergias com projetos de Bioeconomia inovadores, passados e em curso
- Ações de formação e workshops regionais
- Concurso Europeu sobre Bioeconomia

Pilar 3: Modelos de Negócios

- Modelos de planos de negócios específicos para cada tema
- Continuidade dos meios de suporte no pós-projeto

Brochure sides A&B [Macedonian]

Очекувани резултати

- 1 Европска Мрежа за Рурална Биоeкономија
- 4 Регионални Платформи за Биоeкономија
- 20 Успешни Приказни од Руралната Биоeкономија
- 42 работилници за зајакнување на капацитетите
- 4 Регионални работилници
- 1 Предизвик на Европската Биоeкономија
- 440 Интервјуа со корисници/експерти
- 5 Работилници за размена на знаења
- 5 Бизнис модели за Биоeкономија
- Препораки за политики
- > 400 Информативни материјали за Биоeкономијата
- Снимени работилници
- 8 видеа за успешни приказни
- Интеграција во центарот за знаења за Биоeкономијата на ЕУ

Забрзана интеграција на циркуларни био-базирани решенија во руралните региони во Европа

Поврзување на клучните точки за

ОТКЛУЧУВАЊЕ НА ПОТЕНЦИЈАЛОТ

На руралните региони во Европа

на патот кон циркуларна БИОЕКОНОМИЈА

→ Регистрирајте се на платформата за Биоeкономија на БиоРурал за да се вклучите во Европските мрежи за Биоeкономија!

in biorural

fb bioruraleu

yt BioRural channel

biorural.eu

Проект од програмата Хоризонт Европа
1 Септември 2023 – 31 Август 2025

Финансирано од Европска Унија

Вовед

„Биоекономијата подразбира примена на обновливи биолошки ресурси како што се земјоделски култури, шуми, риба, животни и микроорганизми со цел производство на храна, материјали и енергија“ (Европска Комисија) и развиената биоeкономија е клучна во создавањето на циркуларна економија во Европа

Цел

Целта на БиоРурал е формирање на Европска Мрежа на Рурална Биоeкономија за промоција на био-базирани решенија од мал обем во руралните региони и зголемување на уделот на Биоeкономијата

Пристап

БиоРурал е поставен на три столба кои допринесуваат во јавно достапен збир на алатки на Био Рурал

Предизвици

- Нашите економии се базирани на линеарни производствени системи кои користат необновливи извори
- Руралните средини се соочуваат со акутни предизвици (демографски промени, сиромаштија и климатски промени)
- Знаењата за руралната биоeкономија и трансферот на технологија не се соодветно поддржани

....но постојат можности

- Постојат мрежи и решенија за Циркуларната Биоeкономија
- Зголемена поддршка за политиките, истражувањата и иновациите за циркуларната Биоeкономија
- Новите био-базирани решенија континуирано ја поддржуваат транзицијата кон циркуларната економија

Специфични цели:

- Евалуација на моменталната состојба на Европската Биоeкономија
- Идентификација на факторите кои влијаат врз иновацијата, примената и дифузијата на био-базирани решенија
- Создавање на Европска Мрежа за Рурална Биоeкономија
- Проценка и промоција на био-базирани решенија во руралните области
- Овозможување на размена на знаења и градење на капацитети за руралната биоeкономија
- Развој и континуирана оптимизација на отворена дигитална алатка наменета за сите чинители (Збир на алатки на БиоРурал)
- Креирање на насоки и модели за развој на бизниси во биоeкономијата во руралните области од концепт до целосна реализација

Столбови

Столб 1: Знаења

- Анализи на недостатоците на информации
- Работилници за размена на знаења
- Збир на алатки на БиоРурал

Столб 2: Вмрежување

- 4 Регионални Платформи на Рурална Биоeкономија
- Успешни приказни за циркуларноста
- Синергии со завршени и тековни иновативни проекти во биоeкономијата

Столб 3: Бизнис модели

- Бизнис модели за секоја област
- Одржливост по завршување на проектот

Brochure sides A&B [Greek]

Αναμενόμενα αποτελέσματα

- 1 Ευρωπαϊκό δίκτυο αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας
- 4 Περιφερειακές πλατφόρμες Βιοοικονομίας
- 20 επισκεπτόμενα παραδείγματα αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας
- 42 Εργαστήρια ανάπτυξης Ικανοτήτων
- 4 Περιφερειακά εργαστήρια
- 1 Ευρωπαϊκός Διαγωνισμός Βιοοικονομίας
- 440 συνεντεύξεις με τελικούς χρήστες/ειδικούς
- 5 Εργαστήρια ανταλλαγής γνώσεων
- 5 Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα Βιοοικονομίας
- Πολιτικές Συστάσεις
- >400 Υλικό σχετικό με τη Βιοοικονομία
- Μαγνητοσκοπημένα Εργαστήρια
- 8 Βίντεο επισκεπτόμενων επιχειρημάτων βιοοικονομίας
- Ενοσωμάτωση στο Ευρωπαϊκό Κέντρο Γνώσης Βιοοικονομίας

➡ Κάνε εγγραφή στην πλατφόρμα του BioRural για να γίνεις μέλος στα Ευρωπαϊκά δίκτυα βιοοικονομίας!

biorural.eu

[in biorural](https://www.linkedin.com/company/biorural) [@bio_rural](https://twitter.com/bio_rural)
[f bioruraleu](https://www.facebook.com/bioruraleu) [BioRural](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBioRural)
[BioRural channel](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBioRural)

Επιπλέοντας την μετάβαση προς μια κυκλική βιοοικονομία στις αγροτικές περιοχές της Ευρώπης

Συνδέοντας τα σημεία για την

ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΩΝ ΔΥΝΑΤΟΤΗΤΩΝ

των Ευρωπαϊκών αγροτικών περιοχών προς μια κυκλική

ΒΙΟΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΑ

Πρόγραμμα ΟΡΙΖΩΝΤΙΑΣ ΕΥΡΩΠΗ
1 Σεπτεμβρίου 2022 - 31 Αυγούστου 2025

Με τη χρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης

Στοιχεία επικοινωνίας:

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Εισαγωγή

"Βιοοικονομία σημαίνει η χρήση ανανεώσιμων βιολογικών πόρων, όπως οι καλλιέργειες, τα δάση, τα ψάρια, τα ζώα και οι μικροοργανισμοί για την παραγωγή τροφής, υλικών και ενέργειας" (ΕΕ) και μια ακμάζουσα βιοοικονομία αποτελεί το κλειδί για την δημιουργία μιας κυκλικής Ευρωπαϊκής οικονομίας

Στόχος

"Στόχος του BioRural είναι η δημιουργία ενός Ευρωπαϊκού Δικτύου Αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας ώστε να προωθήσει επιχειρήματα Βιοοικονομίας μικρής κλίμακας στις αγροτικές περιοχές αυξάνοντας το μερίδιο της Βιοοικονομίας"

Ευρωπαϊκό Δίκτυο Αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας

Βορειο-Ανατολικό Πολωνία Λιθουανία Λετονία

Βορειο-Δυτικό Ολλανδία Γαλλία Γερμανία Δανία

Νοτιο-Δυτικό Ισπανία Πορτογαλία Ιταλία

Νοτιο-Ανατολικό Ελλάδα Σλοβενία Βόρεια Μακεδονία Ρουμανία

Προέγγιση

Το BioRural επικεντρώνεται σε τρεις πυλώνες που τροφοδοτούν μια δημόσια διαθέσιμη εργαλειοθήκη

Γνώση

Δίκτυο

Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

Προκλήσεις

- Η οικονομία είναι δομημένη σε ένα γραμμικό σύστημα παραγωγής χρησιμοποιώντας μη ανανεώσιμες πηγές
- Οι αγροτικές περιοχές αντιμετωπίζουν μια οξεία δημογραφική κρίση και κλιματικές προκλήσεις
- Η μεταβίβαση της γνώσης και της τεχνολογίας της αγροτικής βιοοικονομίας δεν υποστηρίζεται επαρκώς

...όμως ευκαιρίες υπάρχουν

- Υπάρχουν **Κυκλικές λύσεις Βιοοικονομίας και δίκτυα**
- Αναπτυσσόμενες **πολιτικές, έρευνες και καινοτομίες** που υποστηρίζουν τη βιοοικονομία
- Νέες **βιολογικές προέλευσης καινοτομίες** υποστηρίζουν την μετάβαση σε μια κυκλική οικονομία

Συγκεκριμένοι Στόχοι

- Αξιολόγηση της υφιστάμενης κατάστασης της Ευρωπαϊκής Βιοοικονομίας
- Προσδιορισμός παραγόντων που επηρεάζουν την καινοτομία, την υιοθέτηση και τη διάχυση επιχειρημάτων Βιοοικονομίας
- Δημιουργία Ευρωπαϊκού Δικτύου Βιοοικονομίας
- Αξιολόγηση και προώθηση λύσεων Βιοοικονομίας στον αγροτικό τομέα
- Διεκδίκηση ανταλλαγής γνώσεων και ανάπτυξης ικανοτήτων για την αγροτική βιοοικονομία
- Ανάπτυξη και συνεκτική βελτίωση της ανοικτής διαδικτυακής εργαλειοθήκης
- Δημιουργία προτύπων για αγροτικές επιχειρήσεις βιοοικονομίας από την σύλληψη στην μεγάλη κλίμακα

Πυλώνες

Πυλώνας 1: Γνώση

- Ανάλυση χάσματος πληροφοριών
- Εργαστήρια ανταλλαγής γνώσεων
- Εργαλειοθήκη BioRural

Πυλώνας 2: Δίκτυο

- 4 Περιφερειακές Πλατφόρμες Αγροτικής Βιοοικονομίας
- Επισκεπτόμενα παραδείγματα κυκλικότητας
- Συνέργειες με προηγούμενα ή τρέχοντα πρωτοπόρα επιχειρήματα Βιοοικονομίας
- Περιφερειακά Εργαστήρια Ανάπτυξης Ικανοτήτων και Ευρωπαϊκός Διαγωνισμός Βιοοικονομίας

Πυλώνας 3: Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

- Πρότυπα επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα για κάθε κλάδο βιοοικονομίας
- Βιωσιμότητα μετά το πέρας του έργου

Brochure sides A&B [Polish]

Oczekiwane rezultaty:

- 1 Europejska Sieć Biogospodarki działająca głównie na Obszarach Wiejskich
- 4 Regionalne Platformy Biogospodarki
- 20 Historii Sukcesu Biogospodarki na Obszarach Wiejskich
- 42 Warsztaty dla budowy potencjału
- 4 Warsztaty na poziomie regionalnym
- 1 Wyzwanie dla Europejskiej Biogospodarki
- 440 Ankietowanych ekspertów i praktyków
- 5 Warsztatów służącym wymianie wiedzy
- 5 Modeli biznesowych służących rozwojowi biogospodarki
- Zalecenia i rekomendacje prawne
- >400 Materiałów dotyczących biogospodarki
- Nagrania wideo z warsztatów
- 8 Filmów prezentujących historie sukcesu przedsiębiorstw z sektorów biogospodarki
- Materiały spójne z Unijnym Ośrodkiem Wiedzy na temat Biogospodarki

Przyspieszenie integracji bio-rozwiązań gospodarki cyrkularnej na europejskich obszarach wiejskich

którego celem jest
UWOLNIENIE POTENCJAŁU
europejskich obszarów wiejskich oraz transformacja i dążenie do **BIOGOSPODARKI O OBIEGU ZAMKNIĘTYM**

Projekt realizowany w ramach programu **Horizont Europa**
1 września 2022 – 31 sierpnia 2025

Finansowane przez **Unię Europejską**

➔ Zarejestruj się na platformie biogospodarki utworzonej przez BioRural i dołącz do europejskiej sieci biogospodarki!

biorural.eu

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Wprowadzenie

"Termin biogospodarka oznacza wykorzystywanie odnawialnych zasobów biologicznych, takich jak rośliny uprawne, lasy, ryby, zwierzęta i mikroorganizmy do produkcji żywności, materiałów i energii" (KE), a dobrze prosperująca biogospodarka jest kluczem do stworzenia europejskiej gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym

Wyzwania

- Nasze gospodarki opierają się na systemach produkcji liniowej, wykorzystującej zasoby nieodnawialne
- Obszary wiejskie borykają się z problemami demograficznymi, ubóstwem i skutkami zmian klimatu
- Transfer wiedzy i technologii opartych na biogospodarce do obszarów wiejskich nie jest wystarczająco wspierany

...oraz istniejące szanse

- Dostępne rozwiązania z zakresu biogospodarki cyrkularnej oraz istniejące sieci interesariuszy
- Zwiększone wsparcie w zakresie wdrażanych zmian legislacyjnych, rozwiązań naukowych oraz innowacji dla biogospodarki cyrkularnej
- Innowacyjne bio-rozwiązania wspierające transformację w dążeniu do gospodarki o obiegu zamkniętym

Cel projektu

"Celem projektu BioRural jest utworzenie Europejskiej Sieci Biogospodarki Obszarów Wiejskich dla promowania małoskalowych (niszowych) bio-rozwiązań wdrażanych na obszarach wiejskich i zwiększenia znaczenia biogospodarki na tych terenach"

Cele szczegółowe

- Ocena obecnego stanu biogospodarki na poziomie europejskim
- Identyfikacja czynników wpływających na przyjmowanie i upowszechnianie bio-rozwiązań na obszarach wiejskich
- Utworzenie Europejskiej Sieci Biogospodarki dla Obszarów Wiejskich
- Ocena i promowanie przykładów historii sukcesu bio-rozwiązań stosowanych na obszarach wiejskich
- Ułatwienie wymiany wiedzy i budowa potencjału dla rozwoju biogospodarki na europejskich obszarach wiejskich
- Opracowanie i stała optymalizacja ogólnodostępnych cyfrowych narzędzi dedykowanych dla interesariuszy (Zbiór Narzędzi BioRural)
- Opracowanie projektów skalowania cyrkularnych bio-rozwiązań na obszarach wiejskich

Plan działania

Projekt BioRural opiera się na trzech filarach, które składają się na ogólnodostępny Zestaw Narzędzi BioRural

Filary:

- Wiedza**
 - Analiza braków aktualnej wiedzy
 - Warsztaty służące wymianie wiedzy
 - Zestaw Narzędzi BioRural
- Sieć kontaktów**
 - 4 regionalne Platformy Biogospodarki Obszarów Wiejskich
 - Przykłady historii sukcesu wdrożonych bio-rozwiązań
 - Synergie z poprzednimi i aktualnymi projektami dotyczącymi innowacyjnych zastosowań dla biogospodarki
- Modele Biznesowe**
 - Projekty i propozycje modeli biznesowych dla każdego obszaru tematycznego
 - Trwałość wypracowanych praktyk po zakończeniu projektu

Brochure sides A&B [Danish]

Forventede resultater

- 1 Europæisk netværk for bioøkonomi i landdistrikterne
- 4 Regionale Bioøkonomi platforme
- 20 Succeshistorier om bioøkonomi i landdistrikterne
- 42 Kapacitetsopbyggende workshops
- 4 Regionale workshops
- 1 Europæisk Bioøkonomisk udfordring
- 440 Interviews med brugere/eksperter
- 5 Workshops for vidensudveksling
- 5 Forretningsmodeller for bioøkonomi
- Politiske anbefalinger
- >400 Forskellige materialer om bioøkonomi
- Filmede workshops
- 8 Succeshistorier på video
- Integration med EU's videncentre for Bioøkonomi

bio rural.eu

Registrer dig til BioRural's platform for tilslutning til det Europæiske bioøkonomi netværk

[in bio rural](#)
[@bio_rural](#)
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[BioRural](#)
[BioRural channel](#)

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Fremskyndelse af integrationen af cirkulær biobaserede løsninger i europæiske landdistrikter

Sammenkobling af elementer for at

FRIGØRE POTENTIALT

i de Europæiske landdistrikter i retning af cirkulær BIOØKONOMI

Et Horizon Europe-projekt 1. september 2022 - 31. August 2025

Finansieret af Den Europæiske Union

Introduktion

"Bioøkonomi betyder udnyttelse af vedvarende biologiske resurser, som afgrøder, træ, fisk, dyr og mikroorganismer til fødevarerproduktion, materialer og energi" (EC) og en blomstrende bioøkonomi som en nøgle til at skabe en Europæisk cirkulær økonomi

Wider circular economy (Input, Consumption, Output)

Biobased industries and services

Bioenergy Biomaterials

Biological Feedstock

Forestry, Food & Agriculture, Water

Biobased Innovation

Udfordringer

- Vores økonomier er baseret på lineære produktionssystemer som forbruger ikke vedvarende resurser
- Landdistrikterne står over for akutte udfordringer om demografi, fattigdom og klima
- Viden om bioøkonomi og teknologioverførsel understøttes ikke tilstrækkeligt i landdistrikterne

... men muligheder eksisterer

- Cirkulære bioøkonomiske løsninger og netværk eksisterer
- Øget politik, forskning og innovationsstøtte til en cirkulær bioøkonomi
- Nye biobaserede innovationer støtter hele tiden overgangen til en cirkulær økonomi

Målsætning

"BioRural's mål er at skabe et Europæisk Bioøkonominetwork i landdistrikterne for at fremme mindre bioøkonomiske løsninger i landdistrikterne og øge bioøkonomiens andel"

European Rural Bioeconomy Network

North-West: Netherlands, France, Germany, Denmark

South-West: Spain, Portugal, Italy

North-East: Poland, Lithuania, Latvia

South-East: Greece, Slovenia, North Macedonia, Romania

Specifikke målsætninger

- Evaluere den nuværende status for Europæisk bioøkonomi
- Identificere faktorer, der påvirker indførelsen af innovativ og spredningen af biobaserede løsninger
- Opbygge et europæisk bioøkonomisk netværk i landdistrikterne
- Bedømme og promovere biobaserede løsninger i landdistrikterne
- Fremme vidensdeling og kapacitetsopbygning for bioøkonomien i landdistrikterne
- Udvikle og løbende optimere et online (BioRural værktøjskasse) for interessenter
- Skabe planer for udvikling af bioøkonomivirksomheder fra opstart til fuld skala

Procedure

BioRural er centreret på 3 søjler, som passer i den offentligt tilgængelige BioRural værktøjskasse

Viden

Netværk

BioRural værktøjskasse

Business modeller

Søjler

Søjle 1: Viden

- Analyse af informationsløften
- Workshops med vidensdeling
- BioRural værktøjskasse

Søjle 2: Netværk

- 4 regionale bioøkonomiske platforme i landdistrikterne
- Cirkulære succeshistorier
- Synergier med tidligere og igangværende projekter om innovativ bioøkonomi
- Kapacitetsopbygning og regionale workshops,
- Bioøkonomi udfordring

Pillar 3: Business Models

- Planer for forretningsmodeller for hvert tema
- Bæredygtighed efter projektet

Brochure sides A&B [Dutch]

Verwachte resultaten

- 1 Europees netwerk voor bio-economie in de landbouw
- 4 Regionale platformen voor bio-economie
- 20 Succesverhalen over bio-economie in de landbouw
- 42 workshops gericht op het vergroten van de deskundigheid
- 4 regionale workshops
- 1 Europese bio-economie Uitdaging

- 440 Interviews met eindgebruikers/experts
- 5 Workshops kennisuitwisseling
- 5 Bedrijfsmodellen voor bio-economie
- Aanbevelingen voor de beleidsmakers

- >400 Informatiematerialen over bio-economie
- Gefilmde workshops
- 8 Video's succesverhalen
- Integratie met EU-kenniscentrum voor bio-economie

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Versnellen van de circulaire en biobased oplossingen in Europese landbouwgebieden

De verbindingen tot stand brengen om het **POTENTIEEL** van de Europese landbouw naar een **CIRCULAIRE BIO-ECONOMIE TE ONTWIKKELLEN**

Een Horizon Europa Project
1 september 2022 - 31 augustus 2025

Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie

Introductie

"Een biobased economie betekent het hergebruik van biologische hulpbronnen, zoals gewassen, bossen, vissen, dieren en micro-organismen om voedsel, materialen en energie te produceren" (IEC) en een bloeiende biobased economie is de sleutel tot het creëren van een circulaire Europese economie.

Uitdagingen

- Onze economie is gericht op traditionele productiesystemen die gebruik maken van niet-herbruikbare natuurlijke grondstoffen.
- De landbouw wordt geconfronteerd met acute demografische, klimaatproblemen en soms een slecht verdienmodel.
- De overdracht van kennis en technologie op het gebied van biobased economie in de landbouw wordt onvoldoende ondersteund.

... **Maar er zijn kansen**

- Er bestaan oplossingen en netwerken binnen de kringlooeconomie
- Meer steun voor beleid, onderzoek en innovatie voor een circulaire bio-economie
- Nieuwe biobased innovaties ondersteunen consequent de overgang naar een circulaire economie

Doelstelling

"BioRural heeft als doel een Europees netwerk voor biobased economie in de landbouw te creëren om kleinschalige biobased oplossingen in de landbouw te stimuleren en het aandeel van de biobased economie te vergroten"

Specifieke doelstellingen

- De huidige stand van de Europese bio-economie evalueren
- Factoren in kaart brengen die de toepassing van innovatie en de verspreiding van biobased oplossingen beïnvloeden
- Een Europees netwerk voor biobased economie in de landbouw opzetten
- Biobased oplossingen in de landbouw beoordelen en promoten
- Kennisuitwisseling en het vergroten van deskundigheid voor de biobased landbouwconomie vergemakkelijken
- Een online open tool voor belanghebbenden (BioRural Toolkit) ontwikkelen en voortdurend optimaliseren
- Ontwikkel routekaarten voor bedrijven, die helpen bij de ontwikkeling van biobased landbouw, van idee tot grootschalige uitvoering

Aanpak

BioRural rust op drie pijlers die de basis vormen voor een openbaar toegankelijke BioRural Toolkit

Pijlers

Pijler 1: Kennis

- Analyse van kennishiaten
- Workshops voor kennisuitwisseling
- BioRurale Toolkit

Pijler 2: Netwerk

- 4 regionale platformen voor biobased economie in de landbouw
- Circulaire succesverhalen
- Synergie met eerdere en lopende innovatieve biobased economie projecten
- Opbouw van deskundigheid en regionale workshops, Uitdagingen voor de bio-economie

Pijler 3: Bedrijfsmodellen

- Businessmodellen voor ieder thema
- Blijvende duurzaamheid na projecten

Brochure sides A&B [Spanish]

Laukiami rezultatai

- 1 Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklas
- 4 regioninės bioekonomikos platformos
- 20 kaimo bioekonomikos sėkmės istorijų
- 42 gebėjimų ugdymo seminarai
- 4 regioniniai seminarai
- 1 Europos bioekonomikos iššūkis

- 440 interviu su galutiniais vartotojais ir ekspertais
- 5 keitimosi žiniomis seminarai
- 5 bioekonomikos verslo modeliai
- Politikos rekomendacijos

- >400 informacinių šaltinių apie bioekonomiką
- Filmuoti seminarai
- 8 filmuotos sėkmės istorijos
- Integracija su ES bioekonomikos žinių centru

Žiedinių biosprendimų integravimo į Europos kaimo vietoves spartinimas

Žiedinės
BIOEKONOMIKOS POTENCIALO IŠLAISVINIMAS

Europos kaimo vietovėse užpildžius žinių ir idėjų spragas

→ Prisiregistruokite prie BioRural Bioekonomikos platformos ir prisijunkite prie Europos bioekonomikos tinklų!

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Finansuoja Europos Sąjunga

"Horizon Europe" projektas
2022 m. rugsejo 1 d. - 2025 m. rugpjūčio 31 d.

Introducción

"La bioeconomía comprende las partes de la economía que utilizan recursos biológicos renovables de la tierra y el mar, como cultivos, bosques, peces, animales y microorganismos, para producir alimentos, materiales y energía" (CE), y una bioeconomía próspera es clave para crear una economía Europea plenamente circular

Marco de la bioeconomía (Recursos, Consumo, Subproductos)

Industria y servicios biobasados

Bioenergía Biomateriales

Recursos biológicos

Forestal, agrícola, agroalimentario, acuático

Innovaciones biobasadas

Desafíos

- Nuestra economía se basa en modelos lineales que utilizan recursos no renovables
- Las zonas rurales se enfrentan a la despoblación, reducción de la actividad económica y al cambio climático
- La transferencia de conocimiento y la adopción de tecnología e innovaciones en zonas rurales es un proceso complejo

... pero hay oportunidades

- Las soluciones tecnológicas y los modelos a menudo ya se han desarrollado
- Las políticas, la investigación y la innovación están fuertemente orientadas hacia una economía circular
- Las soluciones innovadoras de base biológica son una oportunidad en la transición a una economía circular

Objetivo

"El objetivo de BioRural es crear una Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural que promueva soluciones biobasadas en pequeña escala para aumentar el papel de la bioeconomía en las zonas rurales"

European Rural Bioeconomy Network

Noroeste: Holanda, Francia, Alemania, Dinamarca

Noreste: Polonia, Lituania, Letonia

Suroeste: España, Portugal, Italia

Sureste: Grecia, Eslovenia, Macedonia del Norte, Rumania

Objetivos específicos

- Evaluar el estado actual de la bioeconomía en Europa
- Identificar los factores que influyen en la adopción y difusión de soluciones biobasadas innovadoras
- Promover las soluciones biobasadas innovadoras aplicables en zonas rurales
- Crear una Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural
- Facilitar el intercambio de conocimientos y la formación en pro de la Bioeconomía rural
- Desarrollo y optimización de una plataforma en línea para los agentes interesados
- Creación de itinerarios estratégicos para puesta en marcha de innovaciones en bioeconomía (del concepto a la aplicación)

Estrategia

BioRural se enfoca en 3 pilares que convergen en una herramienta gratuita: el Kit de Herramientas de BioRural

Conocimiento

Red de contactos

Modelos de negocio

Pillars

Pillar 1: Conocimiento

- Análisis de carencias y necesidades
- Organización de talleres de intercambio
- Kit de herramientas BIORURAL

Pillar 2: Redes de contactos

- 4 plataformas regionales
- Casos de éxito de bioeconomía circular
- Sinergias con proyectos finalizados y en curso centrados en innovaciones en bioeconomía
- Transferencia, talleres internacionales y concurso europeo

Pillar 3: Modelos de negocio

- Dosieres de modelos de negocio para cada área temática de la bioeconomía
- Sostenibilidad tras el proyecto

Brochure sides A&B [Latvian]

Sagaidāmie rezultāti

- 1 Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīkls
- 4 reģionālās bioekonomikas platformas
- 20 lauku bioekonomikas veiksmes stāsti
- 42 kapacitātes stiprināšanas semināri
- 4 reģionālie semināri
- 1 Eiropas bioekonomikas izaicinājums

- 440 intervijas ar galalietotājiem/ekspertiem
- 5 zināšanu apmaiņas semināri
- 5 bioekonomikas uzņēmējdarbības modeļi
- > 400 bioekonomikas materiālu
- 8 veiksmes stāstu video
- Integrācija ar ES bioekonomikas zināšanu centru.

Aprites principos balstītu biorisinājumu veicināšana lauku apvidos Eiropā

Sadarbības veicināšana, lai attīstītu aprites **PRINCIPOS BALSTĪTAS** bioekonomikas potenciālu

EIROPAS LAUKU APVIDOS

"Apvāršņa Eiropa" projekts 2022. gada 1. septembrī - 2025. gada 31. augusts

➔ **Reģistrējieties BioRural Bioeconomy platformā un pievienojieties Eiropas BioEconomy tīklem!**

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Finansē Eiropas Savienība

Ievads

"Bioekonomika nozīmē izmantot atjaunojamus bioloģiskus resursus, piemēram, kultūraugus, mežus, zivis, dzīvniekus un mikroorganismus, lai ražotu pārtiku, materiālus un enerģiju" (EK), un bioekonomikas izaugsme ir būtiska, lai izveidotu Eiropas aprites ekonomiku

Izaicinājumi

- Ekonomika balstās uz lineārām ražošanas sistēmām, kurās izmanto neatjaunojamus resursus
- Lauku apvidi saskaras ar akūtām demogrāfiskām, nabadzības un klimata problēmām
- Lauku bioekonomika, zināšanu un tehnoloģiju nodošana netiek pienācīgi atbalstīta

... Taču iespējas pastāv

- Pastāv aprites bioekonomikas risinājumi un tīkli
- Lielāks politisks, pētniecības un inovācijas atbalsts aprites bioekonomikai
- Jaunas bioloģiskas izcelsmes inovācijas pastāvīgi atbalsta pāreju uz aprites ekonomiku

Mērķi

"BioRural mērķis ir izveidot Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīklu, lai veicinātu maza mēroga bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumus lauku apvidos un palielinātu bioekonomikas īpatnību"

Konkrētie mērķi

- Novērtēt Eiropas bioekonomikas pašreizējo stāvokli
- Identificēt faktoros, kas ietekmē inovāciju pielāgošanos un bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumu izplatīšanu
- Izveidot Eiropas lauku bioekonomikas tīklu
- Novērtēt un veicināt bioloģiskas izcelsmes risinājumus lauku apvidos
- Vaicināt zināšanu apmaiņu un un kapacitātes stiprināšanu lauku bioekonomikas jomā
- Izstrādāt un pastāvīgi optimizēt ieinteresēto personu publisko tiešsaistes rīku (BioRural Toolkit)
- Izveidot lauku attīstības plānus bioekonomikas uzņēmējdarbībai no koncepcijas izstrādes līdz mērogam

Pieeja

BioRural ir virzīts trīs pilāros, kas iekļauti publiski pieejamā BioRural tiešsaistes rīkā

Pilāri

- 1. pilārs: zināšanas**
 - Informācijas trūkuma analīze
 - Zināšanu apmaiņas semināri
 - tiešsaistes rīks BioRural Toolkit
- 2. pilārs: ieinteresēto personu tīkls**
 - 4 reģionālās lauku bioekonomikas platformas
 - Aprites veiksmes stāsti
 - Sinerģija ar iepriekšējiem un pašreizējiem inovatīviem bioekonomikas projektiem
 - Kapacitātes stiprināšanas un reģionālie semināri
- 3. pilārs: biznesa modeļi**
 - Uzņēmējdarbības modeļu plāni katrai bioekonomikas tēmai
 - Pēcprojekta ilgtspēja

Brochure sides A&B [Lithuanian]

Resultados esperados

- 1 Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural - ERBN
- 4 plataformas regionales de la ERBN
- 20 casos de éxito, documentados y compartidos
- 42 talleres de transferencia e intercambio
- 4 talleres internacionales de soluciones innovadoras
- 1 concurso europeo de soluciones innovadoras
- 440 entrevistas a usuarios y expertos
- 5 talleres de intercambio de información
- 5 dossiers con modelos de negocio y recomendaciones políticas
- >400 documentos y videos informativos
- 8 videos de casos de éxito

Integración con el centro de conocimiento para la Bioeconomía de la UE

→ ¡Regístrate en la plataforma de BIORURAL para unirse a la Red Europea de Bioeconomía Rural!

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Acelerando la integración de soluciones circulares biobasadas en zonas rurales en Europa

Conectando los agentes para **DESBLOQUEAR EL POTENCIAL** de zonas rurales Europeas

hacia la **BIOECONOMÍA CIRCULAR**

Un proyecto Horizonte Europa
1 Septiembre 2022 – 31 Agosto 2025

Financiado por la Unión Europea

Įžanga

"Bioekonomika reiškia atsinaujinančių išteklių, tokių kaip pasėliai, miškai, žuvis, gyvūnai ir mikroorganizmai, naudojimą maistui, medžiagoms ir energijai gaminti" (EK), o klestinti bioekonomika yra raktas į Europos žiedinės ekonomikos sukūrimą.

Iššūkiai

- Mūsų ekonomikos yra pagrįstos linijinėmis gamybos sistemomis, naudojančiomis neatsinaujinančius išteklius
- Kaimo vietovės susiduria su dideliais demografiniais, skurdo ir klimato iššūkiais
- Kaimo bioekonomikos žinių ir technologijų perdavimas nėra pakankamai remiamas

... bet yra galimybių

- Egzistuoja žiedinės bioekonomikos sprendimai ir tinklai
- Padidėjusi politikos, tyrimų ir inovacijų parama žiedinei bioekonomikai
- Naujos biologinės naujovės nuosekliai remia perėjimą prie žiedinės ekonomikos

Tikslas

"BioRural tikslas – sukurti Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklą, siekiant skatinti nedidelio masto biosprendimus kaimo vietovėse ir didinti bioekonomikos dalį"

Konkretūs tikslai

- Įvertinti esamą Europos bioekonomikos būklę
- Identifikuoti veiksmus, darančius poveikį naujovių taikymui ir biosprendimų sklaidai
- Sukurti Europos kaimo bioekonomikos tinklą
- Įvertinti ir skatinti biosprendimus kaimo vietovėse
- Palengvinti keitimąsi žiniomis ir gebėjimų ugdymą kaimo bioekonomikoje
- Sukurti ir nuolat optimizuoti internetinį laisvos prieigos suinteresuotųjų žalių įrankį (BioRural Toolkit)
- Sukurti kaimo vystymosi planus nuo idėjos iki platus taikymo su bioekonomika susijusiems verslams

Metodas

BioRural yra sutelktas į tris ramsčius, kurie įtraukiami į viešai prieinamą BioRural priemonių rinkinį

Ramsčiai

1 ramstis: Žinios

- Informacijos stokos analizė
- Keitimasi žiniomis seminarai
- BioRural priemonių rinkinys

2 ramstis: Tinklas

- 4 regioninės kaimo bioekonomikos platformos
- Žiediško sėkmės istorijos
- Sinergija su buvusiais ir vykdomais inovatyviais bioekonomikos projektais
- Gebėjimų ugdymo ir regioniniai seminarai, bioekonomikos iššūkis

3 ramstis: Verslo modeliai

- Verslo modelių vizijos pagal kiekvieną temą
- Tvarumas po projekto

Brochure sides A&B [Romanian]

Rezultate așteptate

- 1 Rețea Europeană de Bioeconomie Rurală
- 4 Platforme Regionale de Bioeconomie
- 20 Cazuri de succes în Bioeconomie Rurală
- 42 Ateliere de lucru de dezvoltare a capacităților
- 4 Ateliere de lucru regionale
- 1 Competiție europeană în bioeconomie
- 440 interviuri cu utilizatori finali/ experți
- 5 ateliere de lucru de schimburi de cunoștințe
- 5 modele de afaceri în bioeconomie
- Recomandări de politici
- > 400 materiale cu tema bioeconomiei
- Ateliere de lucru filmate
- 8 materiale video despre cazuri de succes
- Integrarea rezultatelor în Centrul de cunoștințe în Bioeconomie al UE

➔ **Înscrieți-vă pe platforma Bioeconomy a proiectului BioRural pentru a vă alătura Rețelei Europene de Bioeconomie**

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Stimularea integrării soluțiilor bio-bazate circulare în zonele rurale europene

Crearea condițiilor pentru a **VALORIFICA POTENȚIALUL** zonelor rurale europene prin dezvoltarea **BIOECONOMIEI CIRCULARE**

Proiect Horizon Europe
1 septembrie 2022 - 31 august 2025

Finanțat de Uniunea Europeană

Introducere

"Termenul de bioeconomie se referă la utilizarea resurselor biologice regenerabile de pe uscat și din mare, cum ar fi culturile, produsele forestiere, peștii, animalele și microorganismele, pentru a produce alimente, materiale și energie." (CE) și o bioeconomie prosperă este cheia creării unei economii europene circulare.

Provocări

- Economia noastră se bazează pe modele liniare folosind resurse neregenerabile.
- Zonele rurale se confruntă cu sărăcia, depopularea și schimbările climatice
- Răspândire de cunoștințe referitoare la bioeconomia rurală și transferul de tehnologii nu sunt susținute adecvat

... dar există și oportunități

- Există soluții și rețele de Bioeconomie Circulară
- Susținere din partea de politici, cercetare și inovare în bioeconomia circulară
- Noi inovări bio-bazate susțin în mod consistent tranziția spre o economie circulară

Obiective

"Obiectivul BioRural este de a crea o rețea europeană care să promoveze soluții pentru valorificarea bioeconomiei la scară mică, în vederea creșterii rolului bioeconomiei în zonele rurale."

Obiective specifice

- Evaluarea stadiului actual al bioeconomiei în Europa
- Identificarea factorilor care influențează adoptarea și răspândirea bioeconomiei în zonele rurale
- Crearea unei Rețele europene de Bioeconomie rurală
- Evaluarea și promovarea soluțiilor bio-bazate în zonele rurale
- Facilitarea schimbului de cunoștințe și a formării pentru a crea profesionalism în zonele rurale
- Dezvoltarea și optimizarea unei platforme online pentru părțile interesate
- Crearea de proiecte de afaceri pentru bioeconomie, de la concepție până la aplicarea reală

Abordarea

BioRural se axează pe trei piloni care se integrează în Instrumentul BioRural, accesibil publicului

Piloni

Pilonul 1: Cunoștințe

- Analiza lacunelor de cunoștințe
- Ateliere de lucru de schimb de cunoștințe
- BioRural Toolkit

Pilonul 2: Rețea

- 4 platforme regionale de Bioeconomie Rurală
- Exemple de succes din economia circulară
- Sinergie cu proiecte inovative din bioeconomia circulară
- Ateliere de lucru regionale de dezvoltare a capacităților, competiție europeană de bioeconomie

Pilonul 3: Modele de afaceri

- Proiectare modele de afaceri pentru fiecare temă
- Sustenabilitatea post-proiect

Brochure sides A&B [German]

Erwartete Ergebnisse

- 1 Europäisches Netzwerk an ländlichen Akteuren der Bioökonomie
- 4 Regionale Bioökonomie Plattformen
- 20 Erfolgsgeschichten der ländlichen Bioökonomie
- 42 Workshops zum Kapazitätsaufbau
- 4 Regionale Workshops
- 1 Herausforderung der europäischen Bioökonomie
- 440 Interviews mit Endnutzern/Experten
- 5 Workshops zum Wissensaustausch
- 5 Bioökonomie Geschäftsmodelle
- > 400 Gefilmte Workshops mit Bioökonomie Material
- 8 Videos zu Erfolgsgeschichten

Integration mit dem EU-Wissenszentrum für Bioökonomie

➔ **Registrieren Sie sich auf der BioRural Bioökonomie Plattform, um am europäischen Bioökonomie-Netzwerk teilzunehmen**

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Beschleunigung der Integration bio-basierter Kreislaufösungen in den ländlichen Gebieten Europas

Verknüpfung der Punkte zur

ERSCHLIEßUNG DES POTENZIALS

europäischer, ländlicher Gebiete

für eine kreislauforientierte BIOÖKONOMIE

Horizon Europe Projekt
1. September 2022 – 31. August 2025

Finanziert von der Europäischen Union

Einleitung

Bioökonomie bedeutet die Nutzung erneuerbarer biologischer Ressourcen wie Pflanzen, Wälder, Fische, Tiere und Mikroorganismen zur Erzeugung von Lebensmitteln, Materialien und Energie. Eine florierende Bioökonomie ist der Schlüssel zur Schaffung einer europäischen Kreislaufwirtschaft.

Herausforderungen

- Unsere Volkswirtschaften basieren auf linearen Produktionssystemen, die nicht erneuerbare Ressourcen nutzen
- ländliche Gebiete stehen vor akuten Herausforderungen in Bezug auf Demografie, Armut und Klima
- Der Wissens- und Technologietransfer im Bereich der ländlichen Bioökonomie wird nicht ausreichend gefördert

.... **aber es gibt Möglichkeiten**

- es gibt Lösungen und Netzwerke für die Kreislaufwirtschaft in der Bioökonomie
- verstärkte Unterstützung von Politik, Forschung und Innovation für eine kreislauforientierte Bioökonomie
- neue bio-basierte Innovationen unterstützen konsequent den Übergang zu einer Kreislaufwirtschaft

Zielsetzung

Das Ziel von BioRural ist die Schaffung eines europäischen Netzwerks für die Bioökonomie im ländlichen Raum, um kleine biobasierte Lösungen in ländlichen Gebieten zu fördern und den Anteil der Bioökonomie zu erhöhen.

Spezifische Ziele

- Bewertung des aktuellen Stands der europäischen Bioökonomie
- Ermittlung der Faktoren, die die Übernahme von Innovationen und die Verbreitung von biobasierten Lösungen beeinflussen
- Schaffung eines europäischen Netzwerks für die Bioökonomie im ländlichen Raum
- Bewertung und Förderung bio-basierter Lösungen in ländlichen Gebieten
- Erleichterung des Wissensaustauschs und des Aufbaus von Kapazitäten für die ländliche Bioökonomie
- Entwicklung und kontinuierliche Optimierung eines offenen Online-Tools für Akteure (BioRural Toolkit)
- Erstellung von Entwürfen für die ländliche Entwicklung von Bioökonomie-Unternehmen von der Konzeption bis zur Skalierung

Herangehensweise

Biorural stützt sich auf drei Säulen, die in ein öffentlich zugängliches Biorural-Toolkit einfließen

Säulen

Säule 1: Wissen

- Analyse des Informationsflusses
- Workshops zum Wissensaustausch
- BioRural Toolkit

Säule 2: Netzwerk

- 4 Regionale Bioökonomie Plattformen
- Zirkuläre Erfolgsgeschichten
- Synergien mit vorherigen und laufenden innovativen bio-ökonomischen Projekten
- Kapazitätsaufbauende und regionale Workshops, Herausforderung Bioökonomie

Säule 3: Geschäftsmodelle

- Entwürfe zu Geschäftsmodellen für jedes Thema
- Nachhaltigkeit nach dem Projekt

Brochure sides A&B [Slovenian]

Pričakovani rezultati

- 1 Evropsko omrežje za biogospodarstvo na podeželju
- 4 Regionalne platforme za biogospodarstvo
- 20 Primerov dobrih praks biogospodarstva na podeželju
- 42 Delavnic za krepitev zmogljivosti
- 4 Regionalne delavnice
- 1 Evropski biogospodarski izziv

- 440 intervjujev s končnimi uporabniki/strokovnjaki
- 5 Delavnic z izmenjavo znanja
- 5 Biogospodarskih poslovnih modelov
- Priporočila načrtovalcem podpornih politik

>400 gradiv o biogospodarstvu
Posnete delavnice

- 8 Videoposnetkov s primeri dobrih praks

Sodelovanje z Evropskim centrom znanja za biogospodarstvo v okviru Skupnega raziskovalnega središča

Vključite se v omrežje sodelovanja pri razvoju pametnih biogospodarskih rešitev za evropsko podeželje

biorural.eu

in biorural @bio_rural
f biorural.eu BioRural
y BioRural channel

Kontakt:

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Luka Juvančič
Vodilni raziskovalec za Slovenijo
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Spodbujanje krožnih bio-osnovanih rešitev na evropskem podeželju

Z vzajemnim učenjem in povezovanjem

SPROŠČAMO POTENCIAL

krožnega

BIOGOSPODARSTVA

na evropskem podeželju

Projekt Obzorje Evropa
1. september 2022 - 31. avgust 2025

Financira Evropska unija

Uvod

Biogospodarstvo pomeni uporabo obnovljivih bioloških virov, kot so kmetijski pridelki, gozdno-lesni sortimenti, vodni organizmi, živali in mikroorganizmi, za proizvodnjo hrane, materialov in energije (EC). Uspešno biogospodarstvo je ključno za ustvarjanje krožnega evropskega gospodarstva.

Izzivi

- V gospodarstvu še vedno prevladujejo linearni proizvodni sistemi in poslovni procesi, ki temeljijo na izkoriščanju neobnovljivih (surovinskih, energetskih) virov.
- Podeželje se sooča z neugodnimi demografskimi trendi, zaostrene gospodarske razmere večajo gospodarsko in družbeno razsklojenost.
- Posledice podnebnihih sprememb na kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in z njima povezanih verig vrednosti.
- Sibek prenos znanja in tehnologij za krožno biogospodarstvo na podeželju.

...ampak priložnosti obstajajo

- Razvoj krožnih tehnoloških rešitev in medpanožnega sodelovanja v biogospodarstvu.
- Povečana podpora politikam, raziskavam in inovacijam za krožno biogospodarstvo.
- Nove bio-osnovane inovacije podpirajo prehod v krožno gospodarstvo na podeželju.

Cilji

V projektu BioRural želimo vzpostaviti Evropsko omrežje za biogospodarstvo na podeželju, ki bo spodbujalo razvoj krožnih bio-osnovanih rešitev majhnega obsega na podeželju in prispevalo k večji gospodarski uspešnosti podeželja.

Posebni cilji

- Oceniti trenutno stanje evropskega biogospodarstva
- Identificirati dejavnike, ki vplivajo na sprejemanje in širjenje bio-osnovanih tehnologij in poslovnih modelov
- Ustvariti evropsko omrežje za biogospodarstvo na podeželju
- Oceniti in spodbujati bio-osnovane rešitve na podeželju
- Oljajšati izmenjavo znanja in krepitev zmogljivosti biogospodarstva na podeželju
- Razviti in redno posodabljeni odprto spletno orodje za deležnike/uporabnike (BioRural zbirka orodij)
- Ustvariti načrte za razvoj na podeželju za biogospodarske posle, od koncepta do širše uporabnosti.

Pristop

BioRural temelji na treh stebrih, ki prispevajo v javno dostopno zbirko orodij BioRural.

Stebri:

Steber 1: Znanje

- Analiza vrzeli v znanju in informiranosti
- Delavnice za izmenjavo znanja
- Zbirka orodij BioRural

Steber 2: Omrežje

- 4 regionalne platforme za biogospodarstvo na podeželju
- Uspešne krožne tehnološke rešitve in poslovni modeli
- Sinergije s končnimi in aktualnimi inovativnimi projekti v biogospodarstvu
- Gradnja zmogljivosti in regionalne delavnice, mednarodni natečaj "Biogospodarski izziv"

Steber 3: Poslovni modeli

- Načrti omogočajočih tehnologij in poslovnih modelov za ključne panoge gospodarstva
- Trajnost po projektu

BioRural banner: English version and translations in partners' languages

Banner [English]

Banner [French]

BIOrural
Accélérer les solutions circulaires et biosourcées au sein des zones rurales européennes

Connaissance
Réseautage
Business Models
BIOrural Boîte à outils

Connecter les acteurs pour
LIBÉRER LE POTENTIEL
des zones rurales européennes vers la
BIOÉCONOMIE CIRCULAIRE

 Financé par l'Union européenne
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Italian]

Stimolare l'integrazione delle soluzioni bio-based nell'economia circolare delle aree rurali europee

Informazioni

Network

BIOrural Toolkit

Business Models

Creare le condizioni per
RIMUOVERE GLI OSTACOLI
 Allo sviluppo sostenibile della
BIOECONOMIA
 Nelle aree rurali europee

Finanziato dall'Unione europea
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Portuguese]

Biorural
Apoiando a integração de soluções circulares de base biotecnológica nas áreas rurais da Europa

Conhecimento
Biorural Ferramentas de Apoio
Rede de Partilha
Modelos de Negócio

Ligando os pontos para
DESBLOQUEAR O POTENCIAL
das zonas rurais da Europa
rumo à
BIOECONOMIA CIRCULAR

 Financiado pela União Europeia

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Macedonian]

Забрзана интеграција на циркуларни био-базирани решенија во руралните региони во Европа

Знаења

Бизнис модели

Вирежување

Biorural алатки

Поврзување на клучните точки за
ОТКЛУЧУВАЊЕ НА ПОТЕНЦИЈАЛОТ
 На руралните региони во Европа
 на патот кон циркуларна
БИОЕКОНОМИЈА

 Funded by the European Union
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Greek]

Επιταχύνοντας την μετάβαση προς μια κυκλική βιοοικονομία στις αγροτικές περιοχές της Ευρώπης

Γνώση

Επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα

Δίκτυο

BIOrural Εργαλειοθήκη

Συνδέοντας τα σημεία για την **ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΩΝ ΔΥΝΑΤΟΤΗΤΩΝ** των Ευρωπαϊκών αγροτικών περιοχών προς μια κυκλική **ΒΙΟΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΑ**

Με τη χρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Polish]

BIOrural

Przyspieszenie integracji bio-rozwiązań gospodarki cyrkularnej na europejskich obszarach wiejskich

Wiedza

SIeć kontaktów

BIOrural Zestaw Narzędzi

Modele Biznesowe

którego celem jest
UWOLNIENIE POTENCJAŁU
 europejskich obszarów wiejskich
 oraz transformacja i dążenie do
BIOGOSPODARKI O OBIEGU ZAMKNIĘTYM

 Finansowane przez Unię Europejską
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Danish]

Biorural

Fremskyndelse af integrationen af cirkulær biobaserede løsninger i europæiske landdistrikter

Viden

Netværk

Biorural værktøjskasse

Business modeller

Sammenkobling af elementer for at **FRIGØRE POTENTIALET** i de Europæiske landdistrikter i retning af cirkulær **BIOØKONOMI**

 Finansieret af Den Europæiske Union

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Dutch]

Biorural
 Versnellen van de circulaire en biobased oplossingen in Europese landbouwgebieden

Kennis
 Netwerk
 Biorural Toolkit
 Bedrijfsmodellen

De verbindingen tot stand brengen om het **POTENTIEEL** van de Europese landbouw naar een **CIRCULAIRE BIO-ECONOMIE TE ONTWIKKELEN**

 Gefinancierd door de Europese Unie

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Spanish]

BIOrural
 Accelerando la integración de soluciones
 circulares biobasadas en zonas rurales en Europa.

Conocimiento

Red de contactos

BIOrural
 Kit de herramientas

Modelos de negocio

Conectando a los agentes para
**DESBLOQUEAR
 EL POTENCIAL**
 de zonas rurales Europeas
 hacia la
BIOECONOMÍA CIRCULAR

 Financiado por
 la Unión Europea

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Latvian]

BIOrural

Aprites princips balstītu biorisinājumu veicināšana lauku apvidos Eiropā

zināšanas

BIOrural tiešsaistes rīks

ieinteresētu personu tīkls

biznesa modeļi

Sadarbības veicināšana, lai attīstītu aprites **PRINCIPOS BALSTĪTAS** bioekonomikas potenciālu **EIROPAS LAUKU APVIDOS**

 Finanšu Eiropas Savienība
 <https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Lithuanian]

Biorural
 Žiedinių biosprendimų integravimo |
 Europos kaimo vietoves spartinimas

Žinios
 Tinklas
 Priemonių rinkinys
 Biorural Verslo modeliai

Žiedinės
**BIOEKONOMIKOS
 POTENCIALO
 IŠLAISVINIMAS**
 Europos kaimo vietovėse
 užpildžius žinių ir idėjų spragas

 Finansuoja
 Europos Sąjunga

<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [Romanian]

BIOrural
Stimularea integrării soluțiilor bio-bazate circulare în zonele rurale europene

Cunoștințe
Rețea
BIOrural Instrument
Modele de afaceri

Crearea condițiilor pentru a
**VALORIFICA
POTENȚIALUL**
zonelor rurale europene
prin dezvoltarea
**BIOECONOMIEI
CIRCULARE**

 Finanțat de Uniunea Europeană
<https://biorural.eu>

Banner [German]

Biorural
Beschleunigung der Integration bio-basierter Kreislaufösungen in den ländlichen Gebieten Europas

Wissen
Netzwerk
Geschäftsmodelle
Biorural Toolkit

Verknüpfung der Punkte zur
ERSCHLIEßUNG DES POTENZIALS
europäischer ländlicher
Gebiete für eine
kreislauforientierte
BIOÖKONOMIE

 Finanziert von der Europäischen Union
<https://bioruraleu>

Banner [Slovenian]

BIOrural
Spodbujanje krožnih bio-osnovanih rešitev na evropskem podeželju.

Omreže
Znanje
Poslovni modeli
BIOrural Zbirka orodij

Z vzajemnim učenjem in povezovanjem
SPROŠČAMO POTENCIAL KROŽNEGA BIOGOSPODARSTVA
na evropskem podeželju.

Delphy, Valorial, Nature's Pure, izes, iung, CBE, AIEL, IICO, Valgen, etc.

Financira Evropska unija
<https://biorural.eu>

Press release template

The image shows a two-page press release template. The left page is a blank template with a Biorural logo and 'Press Release | Date' in the top right corner. The right page contains contact information for the Project Communication and Project Coordinator, a social media section, and a footer with the website URL.

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 Tel.: +30 231 046 2885
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 a.balafoutis@certh.gr

Social Media

Facebook	BioRural
Twitter	bio_rural
LinkedIn	BioRural
YouTube	BioRural

www.biorural.eu

Annex D: Deliverable template

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

Enter your deliverable title here

Responsible Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner's short name)]

bioRural.eu

DLX: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101060166
Project Acronym	BioRural
Project Title	Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas
Type of action	CSA - Coordination and Support Actions
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRC-BIO-01-06: Mainstreaming inclusive small-scale bio-based solutions in European rural areas
Start – ending date	1 September 2022 – 31 August 2025
Project Website	https://bioRural.eu/
Work Package	WPs: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Relevant Task(s)	Task Title of the Task
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report; DEC: Websites, press & media actions, videos, etc.; OTHER: Software, etc. PU: Public; SEN: Sensitive; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
Actual Submission Date	DD Month 20YY
Responsible Author	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]
Reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.1	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)
DD/MM/YYYY	V0.X	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)

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DLX: Deliverable Title

BioRural Consortium			
Participant Nr.	Participant organization name	Short name	Country
1	ETHINKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	DELPHY BV	DELPHY	NL
3	ASSOCIATION DU POLE DE COMPETIVITE VALORIAL	VALORIAL	FR
4	NATUREPLAST SAS	NATUREPLAST SAS	FR
5	IZES GGBH	IZES	DE
6	AARIHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY	IUNG-PIB	PL
8	VYTAUTO DIDIZIO UNIVERSITETAS	Vytauto	LT
9	LATVIJAS LAIKSAMNIECIBAS UNIVERSITATE	LLU	LV
10	ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE LA VALORIZACION ENERGETICA DE LA BIOMASA	AVEBIOM	ES
11	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	UC	PT
12	CENTRO DA BIOMASSA PARA A ENERGIA AGROFORESTAL	CBE	PT
13	AIEL ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA ENERGIE AGROFORESTALI	AIEL	IT
14	FOODSCALE HUB GREECE ASSOCIATION FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND INNOVATION ASTIKO MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAREIA	FSH	EL
15	INCOMMON NON-PROFIT CIVIL LAW COMPANY	ICO	SL
16	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL	SI
17	ALGEN, CENTER ZA ALGNE TEHNOLOGIJE, DDO	ALGEN	SI
18	ASOCIATIA GREEN ENERGY	GEA	RO
19	ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJ SLOPIJE	GGP	MK

DLX: Deliverable Title

Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

DLX: Deliverable Title

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3	References	9
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List of Figures

Figure 1: Example caption for figures 6

List of Tables

Table 2: Example caption for tables 8

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
Abbreviation #1	Acronym #1

DLX: Deliverable Title

1 Heading 1

1.1 Heading 2

1.1.1 Heading 3

1.1.1.1 Heading 4

1.1.1.1.1 Heading 5

1.1.1.1.1.1 Heading 6

Title #1	Title #2

Table 1: Example caption for tables

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

Annex E: Event Planning Template

BioRural EVENT PLANNING

Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of, and feel would be well suited for BioRural participation.

BioRural Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BioRural involvement

Annex F: Synergy Mapping Template

BioRural SYNERGY MAPPING

Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.

BioRural Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Annex G: Publication Planning Template

BioRural PUBLICATION PLANNING

Please complete the following form with peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other publication you plan to make.

BioRural Publication Planning			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date

Annex H: BioRural brand book

colors

CMYK

	0 50 100 0
	0 40 60 0
	0 20 100 0
	0 60 60 40
	0 100 100 30
	80 25 100 10
	90 0 100 0
	60 0 95 0
	60 0 5 0
	30 0 10 0

#Hex

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#E1A86E	
#EFCA1E	
#955D4A	
#9A282C	
#66873F	
#54A148	
#92B849	
#8AC5E8	
#C7E2E7	

typeface

iCiel Gotham Thin
(outlined with round corners and round caps)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee
Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt
Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy
Zz

Example

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions
integration in European rural areas

Annex I: Identification of new KERs & IPR process

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation					Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation (how)	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
KER no	Please add any other exploitable results if relevant						For additional KERs please see note for the list of target groups	For additional KERs please describe the means of exploitation.	Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant (one KER might be subject to more than one type of IPR)		
									IPR	IPR	if other please specify